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BSc (Hons) in Software Engineering

International College of Business & Technology

A study of:

Factors that Effect on Public Awareness on Urban Air Quality

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Abstract

Air pollution is the worst thing the world facing day by day. Industrialization and urbanization mainly cause air pollution it will result in climate changes and effects on the people. Building an air quality monitoring and prediction platform is an urgent need to reduce this problem. In this case also people have their part in maintaining clean air. But people can miss this due to not seeing the properties of air and not having knowledge about it. So I would like to propose a solution for all the above problems by this letter. I propose a platform that will be making air quality forecasts, real-time air quality monitoring and mainly providing a learning system. Because knowledge is the most powerful thing and if I can give knowledge to the people they will understand how valuable the maintenance of clean air is. In my proposal, I'll target Colombo, Galle, Matara, and Hambantota a couple of main districts of Sri Lanka. I'm gonna use PM10, PM2.5, CO2, O3, and NO2 as air quality factors and also use Temperature, Humidity, Wind Speed, and Precipitation as metrological factors. I will create a dataset and plan to train an AI data model to make predictions. Also, my proposed system will provide many features to do statistical analysis and analyze graphs easily. It will attract users to my platform and they will get knowledge also.

Keywords: *Air Quality, Monitoring, Prediction, LMS, Air Quality Platform*

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Chapter 01

1. Introduction

1.1. Background of the Project

This project responds to the growing demand for a Geographic Analytics Platform driven by Ethical AI. With increasing environmental concerns and data analytics merging, a platform that combines both is vital for making well-informed decisions.

1.2. Problem Statement

Environmental data analysis often lacks ethics and a centralized platform. This project aims to fill this gap by offering a comprehensive, ethical, and centralized solution for geographic analytics.

1.3. Symptoms of the Problem

The absence of a unified platform results in fragmented data analysis, making it challenging to make informed decisions about air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions.

1.4. Significance of the Project

This project is significant as it has the potential to revolutionize how geographic data is analyzed. It empowers users to make informed decisions while prioritizing ethical considerations in data processing.

1.5. Project Aim

The goal is to create a user-friendly platform using AI and data analytics to provide insights into air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions while adhering to ethical standards.

1.6. Project Objectives

- **To identify Ethical Considerations:** Develop a framework to integrate ethical considerations into the data processing lifecycle.
- **To determine Predictive Modeling Techniques:** Explore effective predictive modeling techniques for accurate and reliable projections.
- **To examine User-Friendly Interfaces:** Design interfaces for easy data exploration catering to users with varying levels of expertise.

- **To identify Centralized Data Processing Strategies:** Establish strategies for consistent and reliable data processing.
- **To determine Real-Time Data Integration:** Investigate the feasibility of integrating real-time data sources for responsiveness to environmental changes.
- **To examine Cross-Domain Collaboration:** Explore mechanisms for collaboration across domains to make holistic decisions.
- **To identify Data Privacy and Security Measures:** Implement robust measures to safeguard sensitive information and comply with data protection regulations.

1.7. Feasibility Studies

For this project proposal, I gathered information from Sri Lankan government websites, mainly from the Meteorological Department, and consulted various internet articles, journals, and blogs to understand the landscape. The aim is to create an Ethical AI-driven Geographic Analytics Platform. Here's a simplified breakdown of the feasibility studies:

1.7.1 Technological Feasibility

I aim to explore the tech side by checking if the Sri Lankan Meteorological Department's systems can handle real-time data and work well with AI and data analytics tools.

1.7.2 Economic Feasibility

I hope to keep things cost-effective by estimating expenses for technology, research, and interface development. I'm also looking into potential returns on investment and long-term sustainability.

1.7.3 Ethical Feasibility

I'm committed to ethical standards. I'll ensure the platform aligns with Sri Lanka's regulations, privacy laws, and data protection policies.

1.7.4 Operational Feasibility

I want the platform to seamlessly integrate with existing systems in Sri Lanka, making operations efficient without causing disruptions.

1.7.5 Social Feasibility

I'm considering public acceptance and stakeholder willingness to embrace AI for environmental management in Sri Lanka.

1.7.6 Environmental Impact

I'm evaluating the platform's potential benefits for environmental well-being and sustainability.

By looking into these areas, I want to demonstrate that the idea is not only technically possible but also viable from an ethical, social, and economic standpoint. The objective is to address environmental issues in Sri Lanka and have a positive influence on geographic analytics.

1.8. Project Limitations

In outlining potential limitations for this project proposal, I acknowledge certain challenges that we hope to address transparently:

1.8.1 Real-Time Data Availability

I recognize the limitation of real-time data availability. Acquiring timely information may pose challenges, affecting the accuracy of our projections.

1.8.2 Budget Constraints

Acknowledging budget constraints, I hope to navigate them by optimizing spending while maintaining the effectiveness and quality of the project.

1.8.3 Data Requirements for Predictive Modeling

There's a need for extensive data for accurate predictive modeling. I aim to manage this limitation by exploring ways to gather comprehensive datasets without compromising on quality.

By openly addressing these limitations, I hope to demonstrate a clear understanding of the challenges and a commitment to finding effective solutions as part of the project's development.

1.9. Risk Identification

Identified risks include potential delays in data collection, the accuracy of predictive models, and the need for ongoing ethical considerations as the platform evolves.

1.10. Work Breakdown Structure

Figure 1 WBS - Work Breakdown Structure

1.11. Resource Allocation Chart

RESOURCE OVERVIEW

RESOURCE STATS

Work status for all work resources.

WORK STATUS

% work done by all the work resources.

RESOURCE STATUS

Remaining work for all work resources.

Name	Start	Finish	Remaining Work
Frontend Developer	Fri 1/12/24	Wed 3/13/24	0 hrs

Figure 2 Resource Allocation Chart

1.12. Gantt chart

Figure 3 Gantt chart

1.13. Completion progress

Figure 4 Project Completion Progress

1.14. Work overview

Figure 5 Work overview

1.15. Budget allocation

COST OVERVIEW

FRI 12/8/23 - MON 4/1/24

COST STATUS
Cost status for top level tasks.

Name	Actual Cost	Remaining Cost	Baseline Cost	Cost	Cost Variance
Ethical AI-Driven Geographic and Analysis Platform	\$70,380.00	\$0.00	\$0.00	\$70,380.00	\$70,380.00

PROGRESS VERSUS COST
Progress made versus the cost spent over time. If % Complete line below the cumulative cost line, your project may be over budget.

COST STATUS
Cost status for all top-level tasks. Is your baseline zero?
[Try setting as baseline](#)

COST OVERRUNS

TASK COST VARIANCE
Cost variance for all top-level tasks in the project.

Name	% Complete	Cost	Baseline Cost	Cost Variance
Ethical AI-Driven Geographic and Analysis Platform	100%	\$70,380.00	\$0.00	\$70,380.00

RESOURCE COST VARIANCE
Cost variance for all the work resources.

Name	Cost	Baseline Cost	Cost Variance
Frontend Developer	\$18,080.00	\$0.00	\$18,080.00
Backend Developer	\$18,375.00	\$0.00	\$18,375.00
Backend Designer	\$4,920.00	\$0.00	\$4,920.00
Frontend Designer	\$4,920.00	\$0.00	\$4,920.00
Analyzer	\$4,900.00	\$0.00	\$4,900.00
Implementation Specialist	\$2,200.00	\$0.00	\$2,200.00
Project Manager	\$11,475.00	\$0.00	\$11,475.00
Tester	\$3,560.00	\$0.00	\$3,560.00
Maintenance Team	\$1,950.00	\$0.00	\$1,950.00

Figure 6 Cost overview and cost overruns

Note: All report files are available in the project folder.

Chapter 02

2. Literature Review

2.1. Theory behind the Problem

Air quality plays a crucial part in the living world. Every living being needs to breathe good air to continue their lives. But unfortunately, nowadays nobody cares about the quality of breathing air and humans are destroying the quality of air for their selfish reasons. The main reason behind the problem is people have conflicts with their air quality knowledge in their areas. That's why we propose a system for monitoring and learning urban air quality.

Value of Air Quality:

Breathing clean air is very essential to our health and welfare. Or else we can get cardiovascular troubles, respiratory disorders, and other health problems. Anyway, despite the importance of air quality some people may not realize it. This is often the result of misinterpreting the abstract nature of air quality and its concrete effects on human health.

Why People Don't Care:

The main reason is its unseen. So that's why people don't notice that. Poor air quality can be affected dangerously, unlike visible problems like noise pollution, littering, etc. People may also believe that authorities and businesses should handle air pollution issues rather than others. Somehow lack of interest in comprehending and enhancing air quality may result from this lack of interpersonal connection too.

Our Mission:

Our mission is to close these misunderstandings, to close this information gap, and also provide a platform with the tools they need to take charge of their environmental well-being. Our goal is to enable everyone to easily relate to, obtain, and, use information about air quality. I think after doing that people will realize their part in avoiding air pollution and how importance of the air quality to continue living in this world.

How Our Platform Helps:

We are offering simple and intuitive user interfaces via our platform for translating intricate data on air quality into meaningful information. Users are guaranteed to obtain the most

recent information by using real-time monitoring technology. Also, our platform provides air quality prediction service and it will help to people foresee changes and take precautionary action.

Our platform is more than just a data presentation tool. It is an instructional tool that promotes environmental knowledge and the importance of maintaining air quality. We are hoping people will take charge of their own lives and make decisions to improve their environment and advance air quality by providing useful advice and data.

2.2. Advantages and Disadvantages of the Proposed System

Sri Lanka has a system to monitor meteorological data but still doesn't have a solution for air pollution. So I'm proposing a system to monitor and make predictions for the urban air quality of Sri Lanka. Here are the advantages and disadvantages of my proposed system.

2.2.1. Advantages

- **Free to everyone**

I'll provide this service as free for everyone. Because every person needs to understand what is the importance of maintaining air quality and what things need to be done for every individual to keep the clean air quality in their areas.

- **Minimizing complexity**

Air Quality measurements and calculations are a bit complex. But I provide solutions for it as well using this platform. This platform provides data to people minimizing the complexity and also calculations are doing the platform by itself.

- **Learning Platform**

I decide to make this platform as a learning source as well. The reason is I didn't find any platform to study air quality data or metrological data in the market. This will be very helpful for students and air quality specialists.

- **Provides real-time data**

Real-time data is very important for these kinds of applications. I decided to get data and publish them to users every hour. This will help users to take action for their living areas according to the quality changing of air in their area.

- **Simple and user-friendly interfaces**

Complex user interfaces are a big problem in similar systems found in the market. Users will lose their paths on these kinds of platforms. So they will ignore the service. That's the reason I decided to make a simple and user-friendly interface.

- **Provides maps**

I'll provide detailed maps for users to get a clear idea about air quality in their living areas.

- **Provides simple and detailed graphs**

People can easily understand graphs rather than statistical analysis. So I'll provide different kinds of graphs for learners in my platform.

- **Easy connections between user and platform**

I'm providing a solution for users to interact with the platform easily. I hope to get users' data through their Google account and once get the data, it will be stored in their browsers as cookies. So users don't need to make logins again and again to send messages, feedback, comments, etc.

2.2.2. Disadvantages

- **Limited access**

Users need to register to the platform to get access to the dashboard. This is for security purposes for the platform and I also tried to give more advanced features to only suitable people. Users need to request dashboard access and the administrator will check their details and they will decide to give them.

- **80% is manual publications**

Up to 80% of this platform's content needs to be manually entered by an administrator. Administrators need to add forecasts manually. Blogs need to be created. Policy statements need to be created. Dynamic content is valuable but sometimes could be a disadvantage on the client side.

- **Age limitation**

This platform is recommended for 16+ users. The reason is the user needs some knowledge to make predictions and air quality measurements and also some mathematical knowledge.

2.3. Current System at the market

As a Sri Lankan in my first attempt, I tried to innovate the new thing most suitable for my country. Then I selected the air pollution problem and researched what things or what systems have us to avoid that problem. But I failed to find a current system for avoiding the air pollution problem increasing day by day. Fortunately, I found a system for a basic system providing metrological information to the people. So I chose that platform as my research project base and got an idea about how can reach people to share information.

I chose a government weather forecasting platform as my project base. It has the weather forecast as the main component. Also provides information about a couple of agricultural areas. Furthermore, it has basic features and functions the same as the normal website. Blogs are an example of that. Especially I found an area in the learning resources section but I wasn't satisfied they provided features in it.

Check [the current system](#).

2.4. Advantages and Disadvantages of the Current System

2.4.1. Advantages

In my aspect, these are the advantages of the current system.

- **Free** - This platform provides services for free to everyone. It's the most advantageous thing in this platform.
- **Simple** - This system is very simple. It's an advantage for platforms that have different kinds of users.
- **Real-time data** - This platform provides real-time data every 3 hours. It's very important when providing dynamic data like environmental metrological data.
- **Knowledge source** - This platform also provides some learning sources. It's not enough actually. But it could be very helpful to newcomers.
- **Multi-languages** - Sri Lanka is a country that has multiple people groups. So multi-language feature is very advantageous for a platform like this.

2.4.2. Disadvantages

After my research here are the disadvantages found in the current system.

- **Less attracts** - This system is very bad for attractivity. It can be a reason to reduce the users of the platform. They didn't care about color themes and used colors that did not match each other.
- **Fewer user experiences** - When I tried to explore the system it was very hard to find the information. That means they didn't care about users' experiences when they developed their system.
- **Not screen friendly** - This platform is made with responsive interfaces. But they are not accurate to every screen. Their navigation bar always made disturbances for users.
- **Ads** - This is a government property. But they play ads on it sometimes. This could make a bad image in users' minds.
- **Too much content** - This platform provides too much unnecessary content. This may cause to miss some important content from users. Too much content is a bad thing for a website.

2.5. Similar Systems at the market

I found a couple of similar systems on the internet for monitoring air quality factors.

- airly.org
- ethera-labs.com
- iqair.com
- oizom.com

All of the systems above mentioned are built to help people monitor air quality and they try to give messages to people about the need to avoid air pollution in the world.

Airly

Figure 7 similar system - airly

They provide their service to government, Companies, and also Communities. They have a variety of services and customers can choose the most suitable. Their goal is to avoid air pollution by making knowledge of people. Also, they thought the first step to face problems is knowledge and education. (Airly, 2024)

Ethera-labs

Figure 8 similar system - ethera labs

They are located in France and provide lab services for air quality. They use the latest technologies when they provide their services including AI predictions.

IQair

Figure 9 similar system - iqair

This is a large-scale platform providing services all around the world. They provide their services on web platforms also mobile applications. They explain how bad is air pollution and how millions of people are affected by it. Their mission is to help governments and the population to give air quality data for free and help to avoid air pollution. (IQair, 2016)

Oizom

Figure 10 similar system - oizom

Oizom is a platform that provides a variety of services. Urban air quality monitoring is one of the big services they provide. They are based in India.

Furthermore, I found the same research papers for air quality monitoring and prediction on the internet.

They say, nowadays, in many countries, air quality getting worse day by day. Industrialization and urbanization are causes of this mainly. So the results of air pollution are climate change and also it affects people's health. So we need to implement a system to monitor and predict the results of air quality are urgent. (Yang & Wang, 2017)

On these problems, we need to build a solution to predict air quality instead of monitoring. So in this case most suitable solution is making a cloud-based real-time prediction platform. According to that we can collect and store air quality factor values on the cloud and we can use stored values to make predictions. (Goh et al., 2021)

2.6. Advantages and Disadvantages of the Similar System

In this case, I'm gonna discuss the advantages and disadvantages in common of similar systems.

2.6.1. Advantages

- **Covering large area** - Most of the similar applications (above mentioned) are world-wide applications. They provide data for every country and it's a very advantageous thing for users.
- **Provides real-time data** - This type of platform very needs thing is real-time data. People need to know what happening or what happens next for the present. So they need to know the latest information about air quality. Averagely above mentioned platforms providing real-time data every 1 hour.
- **Provides attractive user interfaces** - attractive and friendly user interfaces can enhance the user experience on the website. It ay helpful for reaching customers from search engines. Fortunately most of the platforms I above mentioned use friendly and attractive user interfaces for their platforms. (Baker, 2023)
- **Provides forecasts** - Forecasts help people make decisions in their day-to-day life. Most of the above-mentioned platforms provide air quality forecasts also weather forecasts.

- **Makes updates from time to time** - These types of platforms need to provide real-time data and also they need to update their platform data from time to time. It's an advantage for getting people's trust and showing their platforms are active. Most of the similar platforms were updated by this year.

2.6.2. Disadvantages

- **Commercial purposes** - These kinds of platforms do not provide 100% data free of charge because they spend money on maintenance and data gathering. Some are free but mostly they are commercial sites. This could be a disadvantage from the users' side and can reduce the number of users.
- **Complexity** - As proliferation and quality increase, so does complexity. Therefore, the complexity of many similar systems is quite high. This can be disadvantageous on the part of users.
- **Ads** - Nobody likes to get bothered by unnecessary advertisements. But most similar systems use ads on their platforms. The reason is they need to earn money to maintain their services. But from the user side, it can cause them to get bored with the platform.

Chapter 03

3. Methodology

3.1. Functional Requirements

The functional requirements define the essential capabilities of the Geographic Analytics Platform. Here is the list of functional requirements of the proposed platform.

End User:

1. Air Quality Forecast Alert: Users can view the latest forecast on the main page as a main component
2. Average of last 24 hours for factors: The application creates an average of each factor from the past 24 hours and users can see values on the main page.
3. About: The application has a function for end users to read about the platform, authors, creators, and everything.
4. Blog: End users can read the blogs, comment, and like the blogs
5. Latest privacy policy: End users can read the latest user policy. This policy could be updated and will show the latest update date bottom of the policy.
6. Latest terms and conditions: This function works exactly the same as the Latest privacy policy function.
7. Locations: Geographic Analysis platform provides functions to view selected locations on Google Maps.
8. Feedback: The platform provides a function to send feedback to end users.
9. FAQ: End users have a function to read FAQs. These FAQs could be changing.
10. Contact: End users can send inquiries through the platform. The system will get user details from the user's Google account and use them to send messages.
11. Register: End users can request access to the dashboard and after accepting the user's request from the admin, the system automatically sends the credentials to the user.

Registered User:

1. Sign In: Registered users can sign in to the system using system-provided credentials the first time sign in.
2. Monitor Air Quality Data: The platform provides a function to monitor real-time air quality data every 3 minutes.

3. Monitor Metrological Data: The platform provides a function to monitor real-time metrological data as same as the monitoring air quality function.
4. Make Predictions: The system provides functions to make AI predictions for every air quality and metrological factor.
5. Statistical Analysis: The Platform has functions to calculate the mean, mode, and median for each factor. Also provides a correlation matrix.
6. Analyze Graphs: Registered users have a function to analyze graphs for factors and they can select the size of data to analyze. Also has different type of graphs types.
7. Change Credentials: Registered users could change their sign-in credentials.
8. Delete Account: Registered users have a function to permanently delete their accounts.

Administrator:

1. Sign In: Administrators can sign in to the system using HR management-provided credentials.
2. Create Edit and Draft Forecast: Administrators have functions to create, edit, and save drafts for forecasts. Create function can trigger one time when adding the very first forecast. Then administration can continue sharing the forecast with editing. Also, have a function to set the visibility of the forecast.
3. Manage Users: Administrators have functions to read user data, delete users, accept user requests, contact other admins, and add new administrators.
4. Manage Blogs: This platform provides functions to admins to add blogs, view the current blogs list, delete blogs, and edit selected blogs.
5. Manage Feedbacks: Administrators have a function to delete unwanted feedback and get feedbackers' data.
6. Manage FAQs: The Admins of the platform have functions to add, read, delete, and edit FAQs.
7. Change Credentials: The Admins have a function for changing their login credentials.
8. Delete Account: Administrators could delete their self-accounts permanently.

3.2. Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements focus on aspects like performance, security, usability, and scalability. These are critical for ensuring the overall effectiveness of the platform and

enhancing user satisfaction. Here is the list of non-functional requirements of the urban air quality monitoring and prediction platform.

Color Theme

My platform presents two color themes for users. Both color themes are very friendly for users' eye care. The dark theme helps to care for users' eyes in dark environments and the light theme helps to view content perfectly in bright environments.

Figure 11 non-functional - color theme

Simple and attractive user interfaces

Simple interfaces help users navigate everywhere in the web application without getting lost. The application needs to be simple but it also needs to be attractive. Because it helps to attract users to the platform. It will help to advertise the application indirectly too.

Responsive UI

This platform supports any device. It helps to make a large-scale user list around the application. Mobile phones are widely spread all over the world and this application provides a mobile-friendly interface as well.

Figure 12 non-functional – responsive

Security

Security is the main point users worried before entering a website or using an application. This application has very clear user policies and terms. Before browsing the application user can read and agree with the user's policy. Also in technology background, the application is built with the latest security techniques, secured frameworks, and secured routes.

Figure 13 non-functional - security

SEO

As a web application, SEO is very helpful to reach users on the internet. Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction Platform is rich with high-level SEO techniques.

Figure 14 non-functional - seo

SSL

SSL Certificates are very useful for finding secured and Google-recommended websites on the internet. My Platform is hosted with SSL and Google will recommend it to users as well. Users can browse anywhere in my application without bothering any warnings or blocking.

Figure 15 non-functional - ssl

3.3. H/W and S/W Requirements

Hardware and software requirements provide details about the necessary infrastructure, technology stack, and compatibility considerations for the successful deployment and operation of the Geographic Analytics Platform.

Hardware

In the development process, I need a computer or laptop with 8GB RAM capacity. 10GB Disk space and 250GB Hard Drive (SSD is most suitable). Also, need a perfect internet connection and power source.

After building the platform, I'll need a couple of devices with different sizes of screens. Examples: Tablet, Mobile phone, Laptop, Desktop Computer.

Software

In the development process, I need to install a couple of software for building the project.

An IDE - I need an IDE to create both frontend and backend. So I decide to use JetBrains IntelliJ Ultimate IDE. This IDE helps me to create both stacks in one IDE.

NPM - Node Package Manager. I need npm to install libraries and dependencies into my front-end application.

Angular CLI - I need angular CLI to create my front end. I decided to build the front end using the angular framework. Security, Speed, and flexibility are the main reasons behind I chose Angular.

Node - I need to install the node before installing the npm. npm runs on Node.

Java17 - I need to install Java17 because I chose the Spring Boot framework for the backend. A couple of reasons have to choose the Spring Boot. It is a trending framework for web development now. The main reason is security. Spring Boot allows handling request URL endpoints custom.

Python3.10 - I need to install Python SDK for building this application. I have Python data training and prediction part to complete in this application.

PIP - I have to install PIP to install Python libraries into the backend.

In the testing mode and production mode, I need to compatible web browser to browse the web platform on the internet. I can recommend Google Chrome.

3.4. Population

The project targets a population of 1,000,000 individuals, representing diverse demographics, geographical locations, and environmental conditions. This is 10% of the total population in Colombo, Galle, Matara, and Hambantota districts in Sri Lanka.

3.5. Sample Selection Techniques

We can find a lot of sampling techniques. However, I decide to use the Simple Random Sampling technique for this project. Because this application will handed over to a large-scale community. Utilizing the simple random sampling method ensures an unbiased representation of the entire population. This approach minimizes selection bias, offering an equal chance for each individual to be part of the sample.

3.6. Sample Size

The sample size is determined using Morgan's Chart, considering the desired level of confidence and margin of error. This ensures statistical reliability in concluding the selected sample. So I need to collect 384 sample sizes according to the Morgan chart.

Table 3.1
Table for Determining Sample Size of a Known Population

N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	10	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	346
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	354
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	191	1200	291	6000	361
45	40	170	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	180	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	190	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	200	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370
65	56	210	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	220	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	230	144	550	226	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	240	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	250	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	260	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	254	2600	335	1000000	384

Note: N is Population Size; S is Sample Size
Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970

(qhaireenizzati, 2017)

Figure 16 morgan chart

3.7. Sample Composition

People from the four major districts of Sri Lanka - Colombo, Galle, Matara, and Hambantota - make up the sample. This collection offers insights into a variety of environmental elements while capturing regional uniqueness.

3.8. Data Collection Techniques

Direct observations, questionnaires, and the use of pre-existing datasets are all used in the data collection process. This multifaceted strategy guarantees thorough coverage of pertinent environmental data.

3.9. Data Analyzing Techniques

Advanced statistical methods, machine learning algorithms, and Geographic Information System (GIS) technologies are used in the analysis of the gathered data. Mostly using JASP software for graph visualization and statistical analysis. These techniques help to identify trends, correlations, and patterns in the environmental datasets.

3.10. Conceptual Framework

Here is the Factors That Effect on Public Awareness of Urban Air Quality.

Figure 17 conceptual framework

H1: Traditional Media Campaigns: (Ray et al., 2019)

Description: Creating ads and shows on TV, radio, and in newspapers to help more people know about air quality issues in cities.

Justification: Putting info on traditional media can reach many different groups of people. A good campaign can quickly get people's attention and share important details about air quality.

H2: Community Engagement Workshops: (Ward et al., 2022)

Description: Having regular talks and meetings in neighborhoods to tell people why urban air quality is important.

Justification: Meeting with people in their communities helps them understand and care more. Experts can answer questions and encourage people to do things in their local areas.

H3: Collaboration with Schools and Educational Institutions: (Chatzidiakou et al., 2023)

Description: Working together with schools to teach students about air quality and doing campaigns to raise awareness.

Justification: Schools are important places where people come together. Teaching kids can help their families and the whole community. Adding air quality lessons in class can create lasting change.

H4: Online Web Platform for Monitoring and Predicting Urban Air Quality: (Mitreska Jovanovska et al., 2023)

Description: Making a website where people can see the current air quality, past trends, and future predictions in their area.

Justification: Using the internet's easy access and interaction features. The website not only adds to a big database for studying air quality but also helps people make smart choices based on the information.

3.11. Contingency Plan

I need a contingency plan for this research project for several reasons. When I'm doing the research step by step, I could be getting problems. That's the reason I need a contingency plan.

Data collection: In my case, very hard to implement data collection techniques. Because very hard to find air quality experts and air quality data collection techniques. So I decided to generate a dataset for the development process if I failed to integrate a real-time data-gathering technique. I can use Python language to generate a test dataset and also can make correlations between them. Furthermore, I can use an algorithm to generate real-time data from time to time.

Project maintenance: The most dangerous thing is project could crash. Sometimes projects are crashing when using advanced technologies. Version-compatible issues, unsecured libraries, etc. cause those crashes. Maybe after the crash, the project will fail to restore. So I decided to use GitHub as a versioning control technique. I'll update my project partly by part on GitHub and maintain versioning. Somehow if my project crashes in development, I can download the latest successful version and can continue.

Chapter 04

4. Analyzing

In the analysis phase, I used a simple random sampling technique to identify the most effective problem solution. Then I created a questionnaire and sent it to random people and created a result sheet using Microsoft Excel. After collecting the results set to match my target population according to the Morgan chart, I analyzed those results using the IBM SPSS tool.

In my case, I used a pre-created CSV data set for analysis. The very first challenge I faced was all my data were identified from SPSS as Strings. Unfortunately, my very first attempt failed because I could not process statistical analysis for the String values. After a lot of research, I got 2 options to continue my analytical process.

1. Recreate the dataset one by one using SPSS assigning numeric values to labels.
2. Create a new dataset the same as the provided data set using numerical values instead of Strings.

Then I chose the second way to continue my analytical process because it is more accurate and time-saving. Here is the step-by-step process to re-create the data set for analysis.

1. Load the CSV dataset

Figure 18 load CSV to the SPSS

2. Transform data

Figure 19 Re-create the loaded data to numeric

After doing the same steps to all variables, we are ready to analyze with new numerical data values.

Figure 20 Visualization of recreated dataset

Descriptive Statistics demographic factors

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Age_num	384	1.00	5.00	1175.00	3.0599	.06626
Gender_num	384	1.00	2.00	571.00	1.4870	.02554
Employment_status_num	384	1.00	6.00	1304.00	3.3958	.09416
Living_area_num	384	1.00	5.00	1227.00	3.1953	.08055

Valid N (listwise)	384					
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Table 1 Descriptive stats analysis for demographic factors

Descriptive Statistics demographic factors cont.

	Std. Deviation	Skewness	
	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error
Age_num	1.29834	-.061	.125
Gender_num	.50048	.052	.125
Employment_status_num	1.84506	.136	.125
Living_area_num	1.57854	-.237	.125
Valid N (listwise)			

Table 2 Descriptive stats analysis for demographic factors Cont.

Above section provides descriptive statistics for four demographic factors: Age, Gender, Employment Status, and Living Area. For each factor, it provides the number of valid responses (N), minimum and maximum values, sum, mean, and standard deviation. It also includes measures of skewness and their standard errors.

Statistics for demographic factors

	Age_num	Gender_num	Employment_status_num	Living_area_num
N Valid	384	384	384	384
N Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.0599	1.4870	3.3958	3.1953
Median	3.0000	1.0000	3.0000	3.0000
Mode	4.00	1.00	1.00	5.00
Std. Deviation	1.29834	.50048	1.84506	1.57854

Sum	1175.00	571.00	1304.00	1227.00
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Table 3 Frequency analysis for demographic variables

This table presents additional statistics for the same four demographic factors. It shows the number of valid and missing cases for each factor. It provides the mean, median, mode, and standard deviation for each factor. The sum of the values for each factor is also given.

Frequency Analysis for Age

Age_num

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.00	55	14.3	14.3	14.3
2.00	85	22.1	22.1	36.5
3.00	88	22.9	22.9	59.4
4.00	94	24.5	24.5	83.9
5.00	62	16.1	16.1	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 4 Frequency analysis for age

Data dictionary

- 1.0 - Under 18
- 2.0 - 18 to 24
- 3.0 - 25 to 34
- 4.0 - 35 to 44
- 5.0 - 45 and over

Bar plot

Figure 21 Frequency analysis bar plot for age

This section presents a frequency analysis for the "Age_num" variable. It shows the frequency count and percentage for each age group category (1 to 5, representing different age ranges). The valid and cumulative percentages are also provided. A data dictionary is included, mapping the numerical codes (1 to 5) to their respective age group descriptions. A bar plot is provided to visualize the age group frequencies.

Frequency Analysis for Gender

Gender_num

	Frequenc y	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1.00	197	51.3	51.3	51.3
Valid 2.00	187	48.7	48.7	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 5 Frequency analysis for gender

Data dictionary

- 1.0 – Male
- 2.0 – Female

Bar plot

Figure 22 Frequency analysis bar plot for gender

This section provides a frequency analysis for the "Gender_num" variable. It shows the frequency count and percentage for the two gender categories (1 and 2, representing male and female). The valid and cumulative percentages are included. A data dictionary maps the numerical codes (1 and 2) to their respective gender descriptions.

A bar plot visualizes the gender frequencies.

Frequency Analysis for Employment Status

Employment_status_num

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
1.00	83	21.6	21.6	21.6
2.00	64	16.7	16.7	38.3
3.00	67	17.4	17.4	55.7
Valid 4.00	39	10.2	10.2	65.9
5.00	50	13.0	13.0	78.9
6.00	81	21.1	21.1	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 6 Frequency analysis for employment status

Data dictionary

- 1.0 – Employed full-time
- 2.0 – Employed part-time
- 3.0 – Student
- 4.0 – Disabled
- 5.0 – Retired
- 6.0 – Unemployed

Bar plot

Figure 23 Frequency analysis bar plot for employment status

This section focuses on the "Employment_status_num" variable. It presents the frequency count and percentage for each employment status category (1 to 6, representing different employment statuses). The valid and cumulative percentages are provided. A data dictionary explains the numerical codes (1 to 6) and their corresponding employment status descriptions. A bar plot displays the employment status frequencies.

Frequency Analysis for Living Area

Living_area_num

	Frequenc y	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1.00	97	25.3	25.3	25.3
2.00	37	9.6	9.6	34.9
3.00	63	16.4	16.4	51.3
4.00	68	17.7	17.7	69.0
5.00	119	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Table 7 Frequency analysis for living area

Data dictionary

1.0 – Community

2.0 – rural

3.0 – suburb

4.0 – suburban

5.0 – urban

Bar plot

Figure 24 Frequency analysis bar plot for living area

This section analyzes the "Living_area_num" variable. It shows the frequency count and percentage for each living area category (1 to 5, representing different living areas). The valid and cumulative percentages are included. A data dictionary maps the numerical codes (1 to 5) to their respective living area descriptions. A bar plot visualizes the living area frequencies.

Also, I can do the same analysis for all other factors following the above steps. However, I decided to make the analyzing phase more advanced using the 'Compute Variable' option in the SPSS. So I grouped and calculated the mean values by factor categories and then created new data fields.

	demographic	public_awareness	media_campaigns	workshops	coloboration_with_schools	online_platform	var	var	var
7	1.40	2.60	2.60	3.40	3.80	3.60			
8	2.80	4.60	2.80	3.40	3.00	2.20			
9	2.00	3.40	3.40	2.40	3.00	2.80			
10	1.40	3.20	2.60	3.00	2.40	2.00			
11	2.40	3.20	1.80	3.40	3.60	3.20			
12	1.00	2.60	3.20	3.60	2.80	2.60			
13	2.20	3.00	3.80	2.00	2.60	3.40			
14	3.40	3.60	2.80	3.40	3.20	3.20			
15	1.60	4.00	2.40	3.20	3.40	4.60			
16	2.80	2.60	2.40	2.60	2.40	2.60			
17	2.40	3.00	3.80	3.00	2.80	3.00			
18	2.40	4.60	1.40	2.40	2.80	3.20			
19	1.80	3.00	2.80	3.20	1.80	4.80			
20	1.80	3.00	2.60	2.80	2.80	4.00			
21	2.60	4.00	3.20	3.00	2.40	4.20			
22	1.40	2.60	3.60	2.60	2.40	2.80			
23	2.20	2.40	3.80	3.20	3.20	4.00			
24	3.20	4.00	2.60	3.00	3.00	3.20			
25	2.60	3.00	2.00	3.20	3.60	3.80			
26	2.60	4.00	2.40	2.80	2.60	3.00			

Figure 25 Group and get medians by factor

After concatenating the questions by factors, it's very easy to analyze. As above these 6 fields include all of the mean values of factor by user results. Let's do the advanced analysis according to the latest data that was created.

Correlations

		demographic	public_awareness	media_campaigns	workshops	coloboration_with_schools	online_platform
demographic	Pearson Correlation	1	.139**	-.115*	-.076	.120*	.023
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.006	.024	.135	.019	.651
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384
public_awareness	Pearson Correlation	.139**	1	-.054	.064	.169**	-.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006		.294	.211	.001	.422
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384
media_campaigns	Pearson Correlation	-.115*	-.054	1	.110*	-.043	-.054
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.024	.294		.031	.403	.290
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384
workshops	Pearson Correlation	-.076	.064	.110*	1	.009	.008
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.135	.211	.031		.853	.881
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384
coloboration_with_schools	Pearson Correlation	.120*	.169**	-.043	.009	1	-.014
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.019	.001	.403	.853		.787
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384
online_platform	Pearson Correlation	.023	-.041	-.054	.008	-.014	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.651	.422	.290	.881	.787	
	N	384	384	384	384	384	384

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 26 Correlation Map

The correlation maps are very helpful to get an idea about how dataset works with each other factor. According to these relations, we can see positive correlations and also negative correlations between factors. Also, more significant correlations are labeled by the SPSS itself. Pearson correlation is the most popular correlation calculation method and I used it with 2 tails. Also, we can see no missing values in the dataset and every factor correlates with others.

After that, I decided to focus on the main factor, also called the independent variable in the dataset. In my case, it is the public awareness of the urban air quality. The first step I need to configure is whether it is a real-world problem or if it still needs an answer for it.

Statistics

public_awareness

N	Valid	384
	Missing	0
Mean		3.3677
Median		3.4000
Mode		3.00
Std. Deviation		.63804
Sum		1293.20

public_awareness				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1.60	1	.3	.3
	1.80	4	1.0	1.3
	2.00	4	1.0	2.3
	2.20	12	3.1	5.5
	2.40	13	3.4	8.9
	2.60	21	5.5	14.3
	2.80	34	8.9	23.2
	3.00	48	12.5	35.7
	3.20	42	10.9	46.6
	3.40	39	10.2	56.8
	3.60	42	10.9	67.7
	3.80	42	10.9	78.6
	4.00	30	7.8	86.5
	4.20	23	6.0	92.4
	4.40	16	4.2	96.6
	4.60	11	2.9	99.5
	4.80	2	.5	100.0
	Total	384	100.0	100.0

Table 8 Statistics and data representation of public awareness

Figure 27 Histogram for the public awareness

According to the above histogram, we can see a perfect curve and a little bit of tendency for the positive side. It means this is a problem for people and I can go with this analysis. Additionally, I can use a linear regression model if I need to make an AI model for this according to this perfect curve. Also, the tables above perfectly present the statistical analysis data, and I don't waste time repeating that data.

Next, I'm going to analyze how other factors (independent variables) are changed in the people's answers. This step is the most important to identify the people's needs.

		media_campaig ns	workshops	coloboration_wit h_schools	online_platform
N	Valid	384	384	384	384
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		2.7229	2.8516	2.8625	3.3979
Median		2.6000	2.8000	2.8000	3.4000
Mode		2.60	2.80	2.80	3.20
Std. Deviation		.53912	.57005	.54216	.59624
Sum		1045.60	1095.00	1099.20	1304.80

Table 9 statistics for independent variables

Figure 28 Histograms for the independent variables

When we quickly looking the charts of independent factors we can see all of them are normalized and work the same. But when we deeply look at them we can see a lot of differences between them. Media campaigns and workshops have tended to be negative. It means most people avoid those solutions as they are not the most effective. Collaboration with schools has normal distribution and it means people normally agree with that solution. But the solution of the online platform is people are mostly welcome and they strongly agree that the solution is the best.

Training a model for making predictions of public awareness on urban air quality using collected data.

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	online_platform, workshops, coloboration_wit h_schools, media_campaig ns ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: public_awareness

b. All requested variables entered.

Table 10 Variables chart

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.193 ^a	.037	.027	.62939	.037	3.651	4	379	.006

a. Predictors: (Constant), online_platform, workshops, coloboration_with_schools, media_campaigns

b. Dependent Variable: public_awareness

Table 11 Model summary**ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.785	4	1.446	3.651	.006 ^b
	Residual	150.135	379	.396		
	Total	155.920	383			

a. Dependent Variable: public_awareness

b. Predictors: (Constant), online_platform, workshops, coloboration_with_schools, media_campaigns

Table 12 Model test results (ANOVA)**Coefficients^a**

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.927	.341		8.593	.000
	media_campaigns	-.067	.060	-.057	-1.112	.267
	workshops	.077	.057	.069	1.361	.174
	coloboration_with_schools	.194	.059	.165	3.274	.001
	online_platform	-.045	.054	-.042	-.840	.402

a. Dependent Variable: public_awareness

Table 13 Model coefficients**Residuals Statistics^a**

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	3.0954	3.7192	3.3677	.12290	384
Residual	-1.73205	1.51071	.00000	.62610	384
Std. Predicted Value	-2.216	2.860	.000	1.000	384
Std. Residual	-2.752	2.400	.000	.995	384

a. Dependent Variable: public_awareness

Table 14 Model residual stats

Figure 29 Histogram for the trained public awareness variable

Figure 30 P-P plot for standardized residual of public awareness

We have already identified the most suitable model training method for this case is linear regression. So I started to train the dependent variable using linear regression and all steps are provided above. First I identified and assigned variables and got the summary of the model evaluation.

In the model summary, we can see the R score, R-squared score, standard error, and much more helpful statistical information. Also in that table, the summary constants are labeled very well.

Then we can move to the model testing and in this case, we are using the ANOVA testing strategy and then I got the summary of the test results with an F score and sigmoids. Those results are also well-labeled and categorized. We can see 4 values used dependents and 379 values data frame worked as predictors.

After making the coefficient summary stats and residual stats I made the histogram for the predicted model and it looked awesome fitting linear regression. At last, I created a normal P-P plot to visualize regression standardized residuals and it is very fitting to the $mx+c$ linear. All plots are labeled with details like mean, median..., etc.

In addition, find full model evaluation for the test data of air quality and metrological in the [Jupyter Notebook](#).

Chapter 05

5. Designing

Drawing diagram is a bit complex for these kinds of large scale project scenarios. However, I did my best and you can find high quality soft copies in project folder. Also all of diagrams are included in this [repo](#) with source files. (Kindly use these diagrams to analyze the project)

5.1. Flow chart

Figure 31 Flow chart

Figure 32 Flow chart cont.

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

Data dictionary

- 1 - Is cookie stored?
- 2 - Is credentials are correct?
- 3 - Is correctly signed in?
- 4 - Is data correct?
- 5 - Is data found?
- 6 - Is confirmed?
- 7 - Is matched?
- 8 - Is clicked?

System Overview: The Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction System is a web-based platform designed to provide comprehensive insights into air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions while adhering to ethical standards. It aims to facilitate informed decision-making by combining data analytics, predictive modeling, and user-friendly interfaces.

User Roles: The system supports the following user roles:

Admin: Responsible for system administration, user management, and data access control.

Registered User: Can access and interact with the platform's features, including data analysis, predictions, and user settings.

Regular User: Can access to the common features of the website and allows providing feedback, contact, comment by Signing with Google auth.

Core Functionalities:

Admin Login:

The admin can log in to the system using their credentials to access administrative features.

Data Monitoring:

The system monitors and collects data from various sources, including air quality factors (e.g., pollution levels, emissions) and meteorological factors (e.g., temperature, humidity, wind patterns).

Data Analysis:

The platform provides robust data analysis capabilities, allowing users to explore and visualize the collected data through graphs, charts, and other interactive representations.

Data Prediction:

Leveraging advanced predictive modeling techniques, the system can generate forecasts and projections related to air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions.

User Settings:

Users can customize their preferences and settings within the platform, such as configuring notification preferences or selecting data visualization options.

Request Register:

Users can submit requests for specific data or analysis features, which will be reviewed and addressed by the system administrators.

Content Management:

The system includes various content management features, including:

Home: The landing page with an overview of the platform's offerings.

Location: Information and resources specific to different geographic locations.

Blog: A section for sharing news, updates, and articles related to the project's domain.

About: Details about the project, its mission, and the team behind it.

Pages: Additional information pages, such as privacy policy, terms and conditions, FAQ, and references.

Feedback: A mechanism for users to provide feedback, suggestions, or report issues.

Contact: Contact information and channels for reaching out to the support team.

Sign in with Google: An option for users to sign in using their Google accounts.

User Management:

The admin can manage user accounts, including creating new user accounts, assigning roles, and managing access permissions.

Extension Points:

The system architecture is designed to be extensible, allowing for the integration of additional features and functionalities, such as:

Forecast: Advanced forecasting models for various environmental factors.

Blog: A dedicated blog section for sharing news, updates, and insights.

FAQ: A frequently asked questions section for addressing common queries.

Settings: Additional user settings and preferences.

Policy, Terms, and Admin Privacy: Management of policies, terms, and privacy settings for admin users.

Ethical Considerations: As per the project objectives, the system is designed to incorporate ethical considerations throughout the data processing lifecycle, ensuring that data privacy, security, and ethical guidelines are upheld.

Collaboration and Integration: The platform supports cross-domain collaboration and integration with external data sources and systems, enabling a comprehensive and holistic approach to environmental analysis and decision-making.

5.2. ER Diagram

Figure 33 ER diagram

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

Entities:

- Users: This entity represents the users of the system, which can be categorized into two types: regular users and admins.
- Feedback: This entity stores the feedback or comments submitted by users.
- Blog: This entity represents the blog section of the system, where articles or posts can be created, listed, and edited.
- FAQ: This entity stores the frequently asked questions and their corresponding answers.
- Settings: This entity contains various settings and configurations for the system, such as user preferences and admin settings.
- Policy: This entity stores the privacy policy and related information.
- Terms: This entity contains the terms and conditions for using the system.
- Admin Privacy: This entity stores privacy-related settings and configurations specific to admin users.
- Forecast: This entity represents the forecasting models and data used for predictions.
- Home: This entity represents the landing page or homepage of the system.
- About: This entity stores information about the system, its purpose, and the team behind it.
- Pages: This entity represents additional informational pages, such as references and other static content.
- Sign In: This entity handles the sign-in process, including integration with external authentication providers like Google.
- Contact: This entity stores contact information and channels for users to reach out to the support team.

Relationships:

- Users can submit feedback, which is stored in the Feedback entity.
- Users have access to blog posts in the Blog entity.
- Users can access and view the FAQ entity.
- Users can manage their settings through the Settings entity.
- Admins can create, list, and edit blog posts in the Blog entity.

- The system provides a Privacy Policy stored in the Policy entity.
- The system outlines the Terms and Conditions in the Terms entity.
- Admins have access to specific privacy settings through the Admin Privacy entity.
- The system includes a Forecast entity for predictive modeling and forecasting.
- The Home entity represents the landing page accessible to all users.
- Information about the system is stored in the About entity.
- Additional pages and static content are managed through the Pages entity.
- Users can sign in to the system through the Sign In entity, which may include integration with external authentication providers like Google.
- The Contact entity stores information for users to contact the support team.

Assumptions:

- The system skips the handling of comments or feedback from an admin perspective to avoid potential ethical issues related to deleting or editing user comments.
- The location feature is not implemented in the current version of the system but may be added in future developments.
- The diagram represents the core entities and relationships in the system, but additional entities or relationships may exist based on specific requirements or functionality.
- The system follows best practices for data security, user privacy, and compliance with relevant regulations.

The system is designed to be scalable and extensible to accommodate future growth and feature additions.

5.3. UML Diagrams

5.3.1. Use case diagram

Figure 34 UML diagram

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

System Overview: The Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction System is a web-based platform designed to provide comprehensive insights into air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions. It incorporates data analytics, predictive modeling techniques, and user-friendly interfaces while adhering to ethical standards.

Actors: The system involves two primary actors:

Regular User: A user who accesses the system to analyze data, view forecasts, and interact with various features.

Admin User: An administrator responsible for managing the system, user accounts, and performing administrative tasks.

Use Cases:

Regular User:

- Sign Up: Allows new users to create an account and register with the system.
- Sign In: Enables registered users to log in to the system using their credentials or external authentication providers like Google Sign-In.
- View Home: Provides access to the system's homepage, which serves as an entry point and overview.
- View Location: Allows users to access location-specific information and resources.
- View Blog: Grants access to the blog section, where users can read articles, news, and updates related to the project's domain.
- View About: Provides information about the system, its purpose, and the team behind it.
- View Pages: Allows users to access additional informational pages, such as privacy policy, terms and conditions, FAQ, and references.
- Submit Feedback: Enables users to submit feedback, comments, or report issues to the support team.
- View Contact: Provides contact information and channels for users to reach out to the support team.

Admin User:

- Admin Login: Allows administrators to log in to the system using their credentials.
- Manage User Accounts: Enables administrators to manage user accounts, including creating new accounts, assigning roles, and managing permissions.
- Manage Settings: Allows administrators to configure system settings and preferences.
- Manage Data: Enables administrators to perform data maintenance tasks, such as data backups, archiving, or purging.

Common Use Cases:

- Data Monitoring: The system continuously monitors and collects data from various sources, including air quality factors and meteorological factors.
- Data Analysis: Provides data analysis capabilities, allowing users to explore and visualize the collected data through interactive charts, graphs, and maps.
- Data Prediction: Utilizes advanced predictive modeling techniques to generate forecasts and projections related to air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions.
- View User Settings: Allows users to manage their account settings and preferences within the system.

Relationships and Extensions:

- The "Sign Up" and "Sign In" use cases extend the "Regular User" actor, indicating that these actions are performed by regular users.
- The "Admin Login" use case extends the "Admin User" actor, representing the action performed by administrators to access the system.
- The use cases related to data monitoring, analysis, prediction, and user settings are common to both regular users and admin users, as denoted by the generalization relationships.
- The "Manage User Accounts," "Manage Settings," and "Manage Data" use cases are specific to the "Admin User" actor and represent administrative functions.

Credentials (Java class):

This class represents the backend user credentials component of the system.

User (Java class):

This class manages user's data and do CRUD operations.

Admin (Java class):

This class manages privacy settings and user data specific to admin users.

Policy (Java class):

This class handles the privacy policy and related information.

Terms (Java class):

This class deals with the terms and conditions for using the system.

Forecast (Java class):

This class represents the forecasting models and data used for predictions.

Blog (Java class):

This class handles the blog section, including creating, listing, and editing blog posts.

Comments (Java class):

This class is inherits to the blog class and handle comments data for blogs.

FAQ (Java class):

This class manages the frequently asked questions and their corresponding answers.

Feedback (Java class):

This class manages the feedback that gave from registered and non-registered users.

Contact (Java class):

This class stores contact information and channels for users to reach out to the support team.

Metrological (Java class):

This class handles the metrological data that collect from sensors. In this case data collects from auto generated script for testing purposes.

AirQuality (Java class):

This class represents the air quality data of the application and collects same as to the metrological class. Also, handling CRUD operations.

AIModels (Python class):

This class represents the AI models developed in Python.

It has an inheritance relationship with the Metrological and AirQuality classes, indicating that the AI models are integrated with the backend metrological and air quality components.

The class diagram shows the associations and relationships between these Java classes, as well as the inheritance relationship between the Python-based AIModels class and the Java-based UserInterface class. The integration between Python and Java classes is facilitated through the use of the py4j library.

5.3.3. Object diagram

Figure 36 Object diagram

Figure 37 Object diagram cont.

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

The object diagram illustrates the instances of classes and the relationships between these instances in the backend system. Here's a breakdown of the objects and their relationships:

C: Credentials:

This object represents an instance of the Credentials class, which is a Java class.

It is associated with instances of various other Java classes, such as Admin, Policy, Terms, User, Forecast, Blog, FAQ, Feedback, Comment, AirQuality, Metrological, and Contact.

A: Admin:

This object is an instance of the Admin class (Java), managing privacy settings for admin users.

U: User:

This object is an instance of the User class (Java), representing a specific configuration of user settings and data.

UP: Policy:

This object is an instance of the Policy class (Java), containing the privacy policy information.

UT: Terms:

This object is an instance of the Terms class (Java), representing the terms and conditions for using the system.

F: Forecast:

This object is an instance of the Forecast class (Java), containing forecasting models and data.

B: Blog:

This object is an instance of the Blog class (Java), representing a specific blog section with its associated posts and configurations.

FAQ: FAQ:

This object is an instance of the FAQ class (Java), containing frequently asked questions and their answers.

FB: Feedback:

This object is an instance of the Feedback class (Java), providing information about the feedbacks that users provided.

CM: Comment:

This object is an instance of the Comment class (Java), representing a set of comments for Blogs Class.

CO: Contact:

This object is an instance of the Contact class (Java), containing contact information for users.

AQ: AirQuality:

This object is an instance of the AirQuality class (Java), handling the air quality data with importing and test data creating also.

Additionally, it has an instance of the AIModels class, which is a Python class.

M: Metrological:

This object is an instance of the Metrological class (Java), representing the metrological data.

Additionally, it has an instance of the AIModels class, which is a Python class.

The object diagram illustrates the actual instances of these classes and how they are related to each other, while also highlighting the integration between the Java-based backend classes and the Python-based AI models class through the use of the py4j library.

5.3.4. Sequence diagram

Figure 38 Sequence diagram

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

Actors:

Regular User: This represents a user who does not have an account or is not logged in to the system.

Objects:

- Requests: This object handles incoming user requests and routes them to the appropriate components.
- Forecast: This object manages the forecasting models and data used for predictions.
- Latest Data: This object represents the latest data or information related to the system's domain.
- Blog: This object handles the blog section, including creating, listing, and editing blog posts.
- Comment: This object manages user comments or feedback related to blog posts or other content.
- Policy: This object handles the privacy policy and related information.
- Terms: This object deals with the terms and conditions for using the system.
- Google SignIn: This object facilitates the sign-in process through integration with Google's authentication system.
- Contact: This object stores contact information and channels for users to reach out to the support team.
- SignUp: This object handles the user sign-up process and account creation.
- SignIn: This object manages the user sign-in process for registered users.
- Dashboard: This object represents the user dashboard or personalized interface for registered users.
-

Interactions:

- The Regular User sends requests to the system, which are handled by the Requests object.
- The Requests object interacts with various components such as Forecast, Latest Data, Blog, Comment, Policy, and Terms to retrieve and display the relevant information to the Regular User.
- The Regular User can interact with the Blog and Comment objects to view and submit comments or feedback.
- The Regular User can access the Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions through the Policy and Terms objects, respectively.

- The Regular User has the option to sign in using the Google SignIn object, which facilitates authentication with Google's system.
- The Regular User can access the Contact object to obtain information for reaching out to the support team.
- The Regular User can initiate the sign-up process through the SignUp object to create a new account.
- If the Regular User is already registered, they can sign in through the SignIn object.
- Upon successful sign-in, the Regular User is granted access to the Dashboard, which provides personalized features and functionalities.

Assumptions:

- The diagram focuses on the common objects and features accessible to regular users, which are typically visitors or unregistered users.
- The system supports user registration and sign-in functionality, but the details of these processes are not shown in the diagram.
- The system integrates with Google's authentication system for user sign-in, but other authentication methods may also be supported.
- The system includes a blog section with commenting functionality, which is accessible to regular users.
- The system provides access to essential information such as privacy policies, terms and conditions, and contact details for regular users.
- The system offers forecasting and data analysis capabilities, but the specifics of these functionalities are not depicted in the diagram.

Relationships:

- The Regular User interacts with the Requests object to initiate various actions or requests within the system.
- The Requests object communicates with other objects (Forecast, Latest Data, Blog, Comment, Policy, Terms, Google SignIn, Contact) to retrieve and present the requested information or functionality to the Regular User.

- The Regular User can submit comments or feedback through the Comment object, which is associated with the Blog object.
- The Regular User can access the Policy and Terms objects to view the respective information.
- The Regular User can initiate the sign-in process through the Google SignIn object, which likely integrates with Google's authentication APIs or services.
- The Regular User can access the Contact object to obtain information for contacting the support team.
- The Regular User can initiate the sign-up process through the SignUp object, which is likely associated with user account management and authentication components.
- If the Regular User is already registered, they can sign in through the SignIn object, which may be associated with user authentication and session management components.
- Upon successful sign-in, the Regular User gains access to the personalized Dashboard object, which may be associated with various user-specific functionalities and data.

The decision to document only the regular user role is justified by the complexity and large scale of the application. Documenting all user roles and their interactions would require significant time and effort, which may not be feasible or practical in certain situations. By focusing on the common objects and features accessible to regular users, the diagram provides a high-level overview of the system's functionality without getting bogged down in the details of other user roles or specialized features.

5.3.5. Activity diagram

Figure 39 Activity diagram

Figure 40 Activity diagram cont.

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

The diagram starts with the initial process of user authentication or admin authentication.

For regular users, the process involves signing up or signing in, which may include options like Google Sign-In. The user's role is then identified.

For admin users, the process involves a separate admin login, followed by identifying the admin role.

Once authenticated, the system proceeds with data collection and processing, where data from various sources (air quality sensors, meteorological stations, etc.) is collected, preprocessed, validated, and stored in a central repository.

The collected data is then analyzed and visualized through interactive charts, graphs, maps, and filtering options.

Advanced predictive modeling techniques are employed to generate forecasts and projections for air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions, incorporating ethical considerations.

Users can interact with the system, submit feedback or comments, access a blog section, and view relevant information like privacy policies, terms and conditions, and contact details.

For admin users, additional functionalities include managing user accounts and roles, configuring system settings and preferences, monitoring system performance and logs, and performing data maintenance tasks.

Finally, the process ends for both regular users and admin users.

Chapter 06

6. Development

6.1. System architecture

Introduction

The Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction System is a web-based platform that leverages various technologies to provide a comprehensive solution for analyzing, monitoring, and forecasting air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions. The system architecture is designed to be scalable, modular, and extensible, allowing for seamless integration of new features and technologies as the project evolves.

Architecture Overview

The system follows a client-server architecture with a clear separation of concerns between the frontend and backend components. The frontend is developed using Angular, a popular Typescript-based web application framework, while the backend is built using Spring Boot, a robust Java-based framework for building production-ready applications. The system also incorporates Python for developing advanced AI models and leverages py4j, a library that enables seamless integration between Python and Java components.

Frontend Architecture (Angular): The Angular framework is used to develop the user-facing components of the application. The frontend architecture follows a modular and component-based approach, allowing for reusable and maintainable code. The main components of the frontend include:

User Interface Components: These components handle the presentation layer and user interactions, such as displaying data visualizations, charts, maps, and forms.

Service Components: These components encapsulate the business logic and interact with the backend API to fetch and manage data.

Routing Module: This module handles client-side navigation and routing within the application.

Authentication Module: This module manages user authentication and authorization, including integration with external authentication providers like Google Sign-In.

Shared Module: This module contains reusable components, utilities, and services that can be shared across the application.

The Angular frontend communicates with the backend API through HTTP requests, typically using RESTful APIs.

Backend Architecture (Spring Boot): The backend of the system is built using Spring Boot, a powerful Java-based framework that simplifies the development of robust and scalable applications. The backend architecture follows a layered approach, separating concerns into distinct layers:

Presentation Layer (Controllers): This layer handles incoming HTTP requests, validates data, and delegates tasks to the appropriate service layer components.

Service Layer: This layer encapsulates the business logic and orchestrates the flow of data between the presentation layer and the data access layer.

Data Access Layer (Repositories): This layer manages the interaction with the MongoDB database, providing an abstraction over the underlying data storage.

Model Layer: This layer represents the domain models, which are the data structures used throughout the application.

The backend also includes several cross-cutting concerns, such as security, logging, and exception handling, which are implemented using Spring's built-in features and third-party libraries.

Python Integration (py4j): The system incorporates Python for developing advanced AI models and algorithms related to predictive modeling and data analysis. These Python components are integrated with the Java-based backend using py4j, a library that enables seamless communication between Python and Java applications.

The py4j gateway acts as a bridge between the Python and Java components, allowing them to exchange data and invoke each other's methods. This integration enables the backend to

leverage the powerful data analysis and machine learning capabilities of Python while maintaining the robustness and scalability of the Java-based backend.

Database Architecture (MongoDB): The system utilizes MongoDB, a popular NoSQL document-based database, to store and manage the application data. MongoDB's flexible schema and scalability make it well-suited for handling the diverse and potentially unstructured data related to air quality, land use, and meteorological conditions.

The backend communicates with the MongoDB database through the Spring Data MongoDB library, which provides a high-level abstraction and object-mapping capabilities. This abstraction layer simplifies the interaction with the database, reducing boilerplate code and improving overall code maintainability.

Deployment and Scaling: The system is designed to be deployed in a cloud environment, leveraging containerization technologies like Docker and orchestration platforms like Kubernetes. This approach ensures scalability, fault tolerance, and efficient resource utilization.

The frontend components can be deployed as static assets served by a content delivery network (CDN) or a reverse proxy server, while the backend components can be deployed as containerized services within a Kubernetes cluster. The MongoDB database can be hosted as a managed service or deployed as a replicated and sharded cluster, depending on the data volume and performance requirements.

Security and Authentication: The system incorporates various security measures to protect sensitive data and ensure user privacy. The backend implements authentication and authorization mechanisms using industry-standard protocols like OAuth 2.0 and JSON Web Tokens (JWT). The frontend integrates with external authentication providers like Google Sign-In for user authentication, reducing the need to store and manage user credentials.

Additionally, the system adheres to best practices for data encryption, secure communication protocols (HTTPS), and regular security audits to identify and mitigate potential vulnerabilities.

Monitoring and Logging: Effective monitoring and logging strategies are implemented to ensure the system's health and performance. Spring Boot's built-in monitoring and logging capabilities are utilized, along with third-party tools like Prometheus and Slf4j for comprehensive monitoring and alerting.

Logging is implemented at various levels, including application logs, database logs, and infrastructure logs, providing insights into the system's behavior and facilitating debugging and troubleshooting.

Architecture Diagrams: To better illustrate the system architecture, here are two architecture diagrams:

Figure 41 High-level system architecture

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

Figure 42 Detailed component diagram

- [HQ Image](#)
- [Drawio file](#)

These diagrams provide a visual representation of the system components, their interactions, and the overall architecture, aiding in understanding the various layers and their relationships.

Chapter 07

7. Testing

7.1. Test Plan Overview

Project: Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction System

Test Scope: End-to-end testing of the entire system, including frontend, backend, database, and integration components

Test Objective: Verify the system's functionality, performance, security, and compliance with specified requirements

7.2. Test Environments

Development Environment: Used for unit testing and component testing during the development phase

Staging Environment: A replica of the production environment for integration testing and user acceptance testing

Production Environment: The live environment where the system will be deployed and tested for final acceptance

Test Environment Setup and Configuration:

The test environments will be set up and configured according to the following specifications:

Development Environment: Local development machines with the required software installations (e.g., IDEs, databases, runtime environments) and configurations.

Staging Environment: Cloud-based or on-premises servers mimicking the production infrastructure, including web servers, application servers, databases, and any external service integrations.

Production Environment: The actual live servers and infrastructure where the system will be deployed and made available to end-users.

7.3. Test Types

Unit Testing: Testing individual units or components of the system in isolation

Integration Testing: Testing the interaction and communication between different components and modules

Functional Testing: Testing the system's functionality against specified requirements and use cases

Performance Testing: Testing the system's performance under various load conditions and stress scenarios

Security Testing: Testing the system's security measures, including authentication, authorization, and data protection

Usability Testing: Testing the user interface and overall user experience

Compatibility Testing: Testing the system's compatibility with different browsers, devices, and operating systems

Regression Testing: Retesting the system after changes or bug fixes to ensure no new issues are introduced

ID	Test Case	Description	Inspection Date	Tester
T1.0	User Authentication and Authorization	Test cases for user registration, login, and account management	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T1.1	User Authentication and Authorization	Test cases for admin user authentication and access control	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T1.2	User Authentication	Test cases for integration with external	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila

	and Authorization	authentication providers (e.g., Google Sign-In)		
T2.0	Data Collection and Processing	Test cases for collecting data from various sources (air quality sensors, meteorological stations, etc.)	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T2.1	Data Collection and Processing	Test cases for data preprocessing, validation, and storage	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T2.2	Data Collection and Processing	Test cases for handling different data formats and structures	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T3.0	Data Analysis and Visualization	Test cases for displaying interactive charts, graphs, and maps	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T3.1	Data Analysis and Visualization	Test cases for applying filters and customizations to data visualizations	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T3.2	Data Analysis and Visualization	Test cases for handling large volumes of data and ensuring performance	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T4.0	Predictive Modeling	Test cases for various predictive modeling algorithms and techniques	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T4.1	Predictive Modeling	Test cases for generating accurate forecasts and projections	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T4.2	Predictive Modeling	Test cases for incorporating ethical considerations in the modeling process	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T5.0	User Interaction	Test cases for submitting	2024/04/21	Kavindu

	and Feedback	feedback, comments, and reporting issues		Kokila
T5.1	User Interaction and Feedback	Test cases for accessing the blog section and displaying articles	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T5.2	User Interaction and Feedback	Test cases for viewing privacy policies, terms and conditions, and contact information	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T6.0	Admin Functionality	Test cases for managing user accounts and roles	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T6.1	Admin Functionality	Test cases for configuring system settings and preferences	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T6.2	Admin Functionality	Test cases for monitoring system performance and logs	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T6.3	Admin Functionality	Test cases for performing data maintenance tasks (backups, archiving, purging)	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T7.0	Database Testing	Test cases for CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations on the MongoDB database	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T7.1	Database Testing	Test cases for handling large volumes of data and ensuring scalability	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T7.2	Database Testing	Test cases for data consistency and integrity	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T8.0	Integration Testing	Test cases for integrating the Python AI models with the Java backend using	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila

		py4j		
T8.1	Integration Testing	Test cases for testing the communication between frontend and backend components	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T8.2	Integration Testing	Test cases for end-to-end testing of multiple components and workflows	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T9.0	Performance Testing	Test cases for measuring response times under various load conditions	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T9.1	Performance Testing	Test cases for stress testing and identifying performance bottlenecks	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T9.2	Performance Testing	Test cases for load balancing and horizontal scaling	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T10.0	Security Testing	Test cases for testing authentication and authorization mechanisms	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T10.1	Security Testing	Test cases for testing data encryption and secure communication protocols	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T10.2	Security Testing	Test cases for testing vulnerability to common web application threats (e.g., SQL injection, XSS, CSRF)	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T11.0	Usability Testing	Test cases for evaluating the user interface and overall user experience	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T11.1	Usability Testing	Test cases for testing	2024/04/21	Kavindu

		accessibility features and compliance with standards		Kokila
T11.2	Usability Testing	Test cases for testing cross-browser and cross-device compatibility	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T12.0	Regression Testing	Test cases for retesting the system after bug fixes or new feature releases	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila
T12.1	Regression Testing	Test cases for ensuring no new issues are introduced after changes	2024/04/21	Kavindu Kokila

Table 15 Test plan

7.4. Test Cases

1. User authentication and Authorization

Test Case ID	T1.0		
Description	User registration, login, and account management		
Prerequisites	Registration: valid user data and not have a current account. Login: user credentials are available. Management: Successfully logged into the account.		
Test data	Registration:	Login:	
	Name: Kavindu Kokila Email: tester@gmail.com Phone: 0773431660 Country: Sri Lanka Remarks: -	Email: tester@gmail.com Password: 1234	
		Management:	
		Stored cookies	
Steps	Registration: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open application 2. Navigate to 'About' 3. Click 'Sign Up Today' 4. Fill the form with presented test data. 5. Click 'Request' 		
	Login: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open application 2. Navigate to 'Dashboard' 3. Enter presented test credentials 4. Click 'Sign In' 		
	Management: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [login process] 2. Open dashboard 3. Navigate to the 'Settings' 4. [operate change password] 5. [operate delete account] 		
Expected	Register:	Login:	Management:

result	Account requested successfully	Login to the dashboard	[changed password] [account deleted]
Actual result	Register: Account requested	Login: [navigates dashboard]	Management: Password changed Account deleted
Evidence			
Pass/Fail	Register: passed Login: passed Management: passed		

Table 16 Test case T1.0

Test Case ID	T1.1
Description	Admin user authentication and access control
Prerequisites	Admin level account
Test data	Email: test-admin@gmail.com Password: 123456
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login as a user 2. Navigate to the 'Administration' 3. Enter presented test data 4. Click 'Sign In'
Expected result	[navigates to admin panel]
Actual result	[navigates to the administrator panel]

Evidence		
Pass/Fail	Passed	

Table 17 Test case T1.1

Test Case ID	T1.2	
Description	Integration with external authentication providers	
Prerequisites	Not stored Google authenticated cookies and valid Google account	
Test data	-	
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open application 2. Navigates 'Pages' > 'Feedback' 3. [automatically redirects Google auth] 4. Choose and sign in with proper Google account 	
Expected result	Opens the Google sign in page	
Actual result	Opens and ask to choose Google account to sign in	
Evidence		
Pass/Fail	Passed	

Table 18 Test case T1.2

2. Data Collection and Processing

Test Case ID	T2.0
Description	Collecting data from various sources
Prerequisites	Python script to generate test data
Test data	Generated air quality and metrological data
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customize the script 2. Choose model type 3. Run script
Expected result	Created CSV datasets with training models
Actual result	Dataset and models created successfully
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 19 Test case T2.0

Test Case ID	T2.1
Description	Data preprocessing, validation, and storage
Prerequisites	Data generation python script
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customize correlation values and data ranges 2. Run the script
Expected result	Created preprocessed data
Actual result	Created and saved more accurate datasets

Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to the system as a user 2. Navigates to 'Graphs' 3. Choose category 4. Choose requirements
Expected result	Graphs loading to according data
Actual result	Graphs loaded according to chosen values
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 22 Test case T3.0

Test Case ID	T3.1
Description	Applying filters and customizations to data visualizations
Prerequisites	Working API's to gather data from backend
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to the system as a user 2. Navigates to 'Graphs' 3. Choose category 4. Choose factor 5. Choose data size 6. Choose graph type
Expected result	Graphs loading to according customizations
Actual result	Graphs loaded according to chosen customization values

Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 23 Test case T3.1

Test Case ID	T3.2
Description	Handling large volumes of data and ensuring performance
Prerequisites	Working API's to gather data from backend
Test data	-
Steps	[system automatically deletes old data before 3 months]
Expected result	Visualize latest data
Actual result	Loaded only latest air quality and metrological data.
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 24 Test case T3.2

4. Predictive Modeling

Test Case ID	T4.0
Description	Various predictive modeling algorithms and techniques
Prerequisites	Working API's to gather data from backend

Test data	Pm25, Pm10, Co2, No2, O3, temperature, humidity, wind speed, precipitation hypothetical values
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to the system as a user 2. Navigates to 'Prediction' 3. Choose category 4. Select factor to predict 5. Input hypothetical other factors 6. Click 'Predict'
Expected result	Predicted result will appear
Actual result	Predicted result appeared to selected factor
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 25 Test case T4.0

Test Case ID	T4.1
Description	Generating accurate forecasts and projections
Prerequisites	Working API's to gather data from backend
Test data	Pm25, Pm10, Co2, No2, O3, temperature, humidity, wind speed, precipitation hypothetical values
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login to the system as a user 2. Navigates to 'Prediction' 3. Choose category 4. Select factor to predict 5. Input hypothetical other factors 6. Click 'Predict'
Expected	Predicted result will appear

result	
Actual result	Predicted result appeared to selected factor
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 26 Test case T4.1

Test Case ID	T4.2
Description	Incorporating ethical considerations in the modeling process
Prerequisites	-
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opens the application 2. Navigates to 'Pages' > 'References'
Expected result	Model documentation and evaluation found
Actual result	Found well documented documentation explaining everything and accuracy of models and examples.
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 27 Test case T4.2

5. User Interaction and Feedback

Test Case ID	T5.0
Description	Submitting feedback, comments, and reporting issues
Prerequisites	Signed into the app using Google Auth
Test data	Feedback: This is a good application Comment: Nice blog
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opens the application 2. Navigates to 'Pages' > 'Feedback' 3. Add feedback 4. Click 'Submit' 5. Navigates to 'Blog' 6. Choose blog 7. Add comment 8. Click 'Comment'
Expected result	Feedback added and comments added
Actual result	Feedback added and visualize instantly Comment added successfully and visualize instantly
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 28 Test case T5.0

Test Case ID	T5.1
Description	Accessing the blog section and displaying articles
Prerequisites	Signed into the app using Google Auth
Test data	-

Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opens the application 2. Navigates to 'Blog' 3. Choose blog
Expected result	Displayed chosen blog
Actual result	Chosen Blog/ Article displayed with comment section
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 29 Test case T5.1

Test Case ID	T5.2
Description	Viewing privacy policies, terms and conditions, and contact information
Prerequisites	Signed into the app using Google Auth
Test data	Name: kavindu Kokila Email: kkavindu221@gmail.com Message: I like to contribute on this project
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opens the application 2. Navigates to 'Pages' > 'Privacy Policy' 3. Navigates to 'Pages' > 'Terms & Conditions' 4. Navigates to 'Contact' 5. Add valid data 6. Click 'Send Message'
Expected result	Displaying Privacy Policy and Terms and conditions Contact message send successfully
Actual result	Displayed latest privacy policy and terms and conditions Contact message sent successfully

Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 30 Test case T5.2

6. Admin Functionality

Test Case ID	T6.0
Description	Managing user accounts and roles
Prerequisites	Signed into the app as administration
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login as a user 2. Navigates to 'Administration' 3. Login as administration 4. Navigates to 'Users' 5. Choose managing option
Expected result	Can manage regular users and admin users with CRUD operations.
Actual result	Can approve, delete, create, contact users.
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 31 Test case T6.0

Test Case ID	T6.1
Description	Configuring system settings and preferences
Prerequisites	Signed into the app as administration
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login as administration 2. Navigates to 'Settings' 3. Choose option
Expected result	Can manage system settings
Actual result	Admin can change or create user terms, user policy and custom settings.
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 32 Test case T6.1

Test Case ID	T6.2
Description	Monitoring system performance and logs
Prerequisites	Signed into the app as administration
Test data	-
Steps	[Not Found]
Expected result	Can monitoring system performance
Actual result	[Not found]
Evidence	-
Pass/Fail	Failed

Table 33 Test case T6.2

Test Case ID	T6.3
Description	Performing data maintenance tasks (backups, archiving, purging)
Prerequisites	Signed into the app as administration
Test data	-
Steps	[Not Found]
Expected result	Can maintain system data
Actual result	[Not found]
Evidence	-
Pass/Fail	Failed

Table 34 Test case T6.3

7. Database Testing

Test Case ID	T7.0
Description	CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations on the MongoDB database
Prerequisites	Working APIs for CRUD Operations
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open POSTMAN 2. Create request with according request method 3. Enter API with params or request body values 4. Click 'OK'
Expected result	All request method working
Actual result	All APIs works correctly and data fetched successfully
Evidence	

Pass/Fail	Passed
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Table 35 Test case T7.0

Test Case ID	T7.1
Description	Handling large volumes of data and ensuring scalability
Prerequisites	Working APIs for handle formdata
Test data	CSV Dataset
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open POSTMAN 2. Create request with provided form data 3. Enter API 4. Click 'OK'
Expected result	CSV file extracting and storing all data in database
Actual result	All data rows stored in database
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 36 Test case T7.1

Test Case ID	T7.2
Description	Data consistency and integrity
Prerequisites	-
Test data	-
Steps	[This is system automated]
Expected result	Data generating every hour
Actual result	Data generated and stored in database every hour

Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 37 Test case T7.2

8. Integration Testing

Test Case ID	T8.0
Description	Integrating the Python AI models with the Java backend using py4j
Prerequisites	Installed py4j library
Test data	-
Steps	[This is system automated]
Expected result	Passing received values to the AI models
Actual result	Getting received values from java classes and make predictions and returns predicted values
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 38 Test case T8.0

Test Case ID	T8.1
Description	Testing the communication between frontend and backend components

Prerequisites	Stared to run both backend and frontend services
Test data	-
Steps	[This is system automated]
Expected result	Connecting and fetching data from database
Actual result	Closed the loading effect and fetch data to the client
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 39 Test case T8.1

Test Case ID	T8.2
Description	End-to-end testing of multiple components and workflows
Prerequisites	Stared to run both backend and frontend services and working APIs
Test data	All testing values and APIs
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Opens the postman 2. Check all APIs one-by-one
Expected result	API Testing document finds here
Actual result	API Testing document finds here
Evidence	API Testing document
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 40 Test case T8.2

9. Performance Testing

Test Case ID	T9.0
Description	Measuring response times under various load conditions

Prerequisites	Application in production mode and lighthouse extension
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Browse the application on internet 2. Open lighthouse extension 3. Generate report
Expected result	Up to 50% performance
Actual result	27% performance
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Failed

Table 41 Test case T9.0

Test Case ID	T9.1
Description	Stress testing and identifying performance bottlenecks
Prerequisites	Application in production mode and lighthouse extension
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Browse the application on internet 2. Open lighthouse extension 3. Generate report
Expected result	<p>First contentful paint – 3s</p> <p>Largest contentful paint – 4.2s</p> <p>Total blocking time – 220ms</p> <p>Speed index – 5s</p>
Actual result	<p>First contentful paint – 5.4s</p> <p>Largest contentful paint – 8.8s</p> <p>Total blocking time – 350ms</p>

	Speed index – 7.9s
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Failed

Table 42 Test case T9.1

Test Case ID	T9.2
Description	Load balancing and horizontal scaling
Prerequisites	Application in production mode and inspect mode browser
Test data	-
Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Browse the application on internet 2. Open inspect panel 3. Change screen size
Expected result	Responsive and works in every screen
Actual result	Responsive and worked in every screen without any damaged
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 43 Test case T9.2

10. Security Testing

Test Case ID	T10.0
Description	Testing authentication and authorization mechanisms
Prerequisites	Logged out from the application and cleared all cookies
Test data	Username: tester@gmail.com Password: 1234
Steps	[same as to the test case ID – T1.0(login)]
Expected result	Logging in to the system
Actual result	Logged in to the system and cookies stored
Evidence	A screenshot of a web browser window showing a successful login. The browser's developer console is open, displaying a list of cookies stored on the device. The cookies include session identifiers, user information, and other application-specific data. The browser interface shows a city forecast page, indicating the user is logged in and viewing content.
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 44 Test case T10.0

Test Case ID	T10.1
Description	Testing data encryption and secure communication protocols
Prerequisites	Logged in to the system
Test data	-
Steps	[system automated]
Expected result	Blocking unauthorized endpoints
Actual result	Blocked unauthorized end points and only can access to the data from provided frontend endpoint.

Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 45 Test case T10.1

Test Case ID	T10.2
Description	Testing vulnerability to common web application threats
Prerequisites	SSL Certificate
Test data	-
Steps	-
Expected result	Block harmful APIs by CORS policy
Actual result	Remove harmful requests from SSL and SQL injections are not working because this application works with NoSQL. Application allows only repository method that system allowed
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 46 Test case T10.2

11. Usability Testing

Test Case ID	T11.0
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Description	Evaluating the user interface and overall user experience
Prerequisites	Logged as user and logged as administrator Stored Google sign in cookies
Test data	application
Steps	[browse application every each page]
Expected result	User friendly and easily understand interfaces
Actual result	Interfaces are very user friendly and anyone can understand even without user manual.
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 47 Test case T11.0

Test Case ID	T11.1
Description	Testing accessibility features and compliance with standards
Prerequisites	Logged as user and logged as administrator Stored Google sign in cookies
Test data	application
Steps	[browse application every each page]
Expected result	Application has standards and policies
Actual result	Application meets the web application standers and latest terms and policies.

Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 48 Test case T11.1

Test Case ID	T11.2
Description	Testing cross-browser and cross-device compatibility
Prerequisites	Logged as user and logged as administrator Stored Google sign in cookies
Test data	application
Steps	[browse application every each page]
Expected result	Application can work in different browsers and different devices
Actual result	Application works with any device and any browser without any damage
Evidence	
Pass/Fail	Passed

Table 49 Test case T11.2

7.5. Test Data Setup and Management

Test data will be generated using a combination of scripting tools and manual data entry processes.

Sensitive data will be obfuscated or anonymized using data masking techniques to ensure data privacy and security.

A dedicated test data management system will be used to store, manipulate, and version control test data throughout the testing lifecycle.

7.6. Test Automation

Unit tests and integration tests will be automated using the appropriate frameworks and tools (e.g., JUnit, Mockito for Java, pytest for Python).

UI testing will be automated using Selenium or Cypress for browser-based testing and Appium for mobile app testing.

A continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipeline will be set up to enable automated execution of tests during the build and deployment processes.

Non-Functional Testing:

In addition to performance and security testing, the following non-functional testing activities will be performed:

Compatibility Testing: Verifying the system's compatibility with different operating systems, browsers, and devices.

Reliability Testing: Ensuring the system's ability to operate consistently and recover from failures or errors.

Localization/Internationalization Testing: Validating the system's support for multiple languages and locales.

7.7. Test Data Analysis and Reporting

Test results and data will be analyzed using specialized reporting tools and dashboards (e.g., TestRail, qTest).

Detailed test reports, including metrics, defects, and trends, will be generated and shared with stakeholders on a weekly basis.

Real-time test execution status and progress will be visible to the team through the chosen reporting platform.

7.8. Risk Management and Mitigation

Potential risks associated with the testing process have been identified, and mitigation strategies will be implemented. These risks include:

Resource Constraints: Ensure adequate staffing and allocation of resources for testing activities.

Schedule Delays: Implement proactive risk monitoring and adjust the testing schedule as needed.

Environmental Factors: Establish contingency plans for potential infrastructure or service disruptions.

External Dependencies: Maintain close communication with external service providers and plan for alternative solutions if needed.

7.9. Test Effort Estimation

The estimated effort for executing the planned test cases is as follows:

Unit Testing: 2 person-weeks

Integration Testing: 3 person-weeks

Functional Testing: 4 person-weeks

Performance Testing: 2 person-weeks

Security Testing: 1 person-week

Usability Testing: 1 person-week

Regression Testing: 2 person-weeks

Note: The effort estimates may vary based on the actual complexity and scope of the test cases.

7.10. Test Management and Reporting

Test management tools (e.g., Postman) will be used for organizing and tracking test cases

Automated testing frameworks (e.g., Selenium, Cypress) will be utilized for efficient execution of test cases

Test reports will be generated and shared with stakeholders regularly

Defect tracking and management tools (e.g., Jira, slf4j, ngxLogger) will be used to log and track identified issues

7.11. Test Acceptance Criteria

All critical and high-priority test cases must pass

System performance should meet the specified requirements and benchmarks

Security vulnerabilities identified during testing should be addressed and mitigated

User experience and usability should meet the defined standards and stakeholder expectations

7.12. Test Exit Criteria

All planned test cases have been executed, and their results documented

All critical and high-priority defects have been resolved or accepted by stakeholders

System performance meets the specified requirements and benchmarks

The system has passed user acceptance testing and received sign-off from stakeholders

Regarding the "[not found]" cases (T6.2 and T6.3), these test cases will be developed further as part of future iterations or releases of the system. The current version of the test plan does not include specific details for these test cases, but they will be added and expanded upon in subsequent updates.

For the failed performance test cases (T9.0 and T9.1), the failure is due to hosting the application on free servers with limited resources and capabilities. These test cases should be re-evaluated when the application is deployed in a production-like environment with adequate resources and infrastructure to ensure accurate performance testing results.

Chapter 08

8. Implementation

8.1. Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the implementation details for the Urban Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction System. It covers the system architecture, technologies used, and the implementation approach for various components and features.

8.2. System Architecture

The system follows client-server architecture with a modular design. The main components are:

8.2.1. Frontend

Angular: An open-source java script framework that using typescript.

RxJS: A library that helping to reactive programming using observables.

Material-UI: A popular Angular UI framework for implementing material design.

8.2.2. Backend

Java: The primary programming language for the backend.

Spring Boot: A framework for building production-grade applications.

Spring Data MongoDB: A framework for integrating with MongoDB database.

py4j: A library for integrating Python components with Java.

8.2.3. Database

MongoDB: A NoSQL database for storing air quality data and user information.

8.2.4. AI Models

Python: The programming language used for implementing AI models.

TensorFlow: A popular machine learning library for building and training models.

Scikit-learn: A machine learning library for data preprocessing and modeling.

8.3. Implementation Details

8.3.1. User Authentication and Authorization

User registration and login functionality is implemented using JSON Web Tokens (JWT) for stateless authentication.

Role-based access control (RBAC) is implemented to restrict access to certain features based on user roles (e.g., admin, regular user).

Integration with external authentication providers (e.g., Google Sign-In) is implemented using OAuth 2.0.

8.3.2. Data Collection and Processing

Air quality data is collected from various sources, such as meteorological stations and using generating patterns, using RESTful APIs or direct database integration.

Data preprocessing tasks, such as cleaning, normalization, and validation, are performed using Python scripts.

Processed data is stored in the MongoDB database for further analysis and visualization.

8.3.3. Data Analysis and Visualization

Interactive charts, graphs, and maps are rendered using Angular components and popular data visualization libraries (e.g., Chart.js).

Filtering and customization options are provided for users to interact with the visualizations.

Large volumes of data are handled efficiently using techniques like pagination and lazy loading.

8.3.4. Predictive Modeling

AI models for air quality prediction are developed using Python libraries like TensorFlow and Scikit-learn.

Models are trained on historical air quality data and meteorological data.

The py4j library is used to integrate the Python AI models with the Java backend, enabling seamless communication between the two components.

Users can input hypothetical values or scenarios, and the AI models generate accurate forecasts and projections.

8.3.5. User Interaction and Feedback

A feedback and comments section is implemented using MongoDB for storing user submissions.

A blog section is integrated, allowing administrators to publish articles and users to leave comments.

Privacy policies, terms and conditions, and contact information are displayed and managed through the admin panel.

8.3.6. Admin Functionality

Admin users can manage regular user accounts, roles, and access permissions through a dedicated admin panel.

System settings and preferences can be configured by admin users.

Monitoring system performance and logs is implemented using logging frameworks like SLF4J and ngx-logger.

8.3.7. Database Integration

The Spring Data MongoDB library is used for seamless integration with the MongoDB database.

CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations are implemented using repository interfaces and custom queries.

Handling large volumes of data and ensuring scalability is achieved through techniques like sharding and horizontal scaling.

Data consistency and integrity are maintained through validation rules and constraints enforced at the database level.

8.3.8. Integration and Communication

The py4j library is used for integrating the Python AI models with the Java backend components.

Communication between the frontend and backend components is facilitated through RESTful APIs and WebSockets.

End-to-end testing of multiple components and workflows is performed using automated testing frameworks like Selenium and Cypress.

8.3.9. Performance Optimization

Caching strategies are implemented to improve response times and reduce database load.

Load balancing and horizontal scaling techniques are employed to handle high traffic and ensure system availability.

Code optimizations and performance profiling are conducted to identify and mitigate performance bottlenecks.

8.3.10. Security

Authentication and authorization mechanisms are implemented using industry-standard practices (e.g., JWT, RBAC).

Data encryption and secure communication protocols (e.g., HTTPS, SSL/TLS) are employed to protect sensitive information.

Regular vulnerability assessments and penetration testing are conducted to identify and mitigate potential security threats.

8.3.11. Usability and Accessibility

User interface design follows best practices for usability and accessibility.

Compliance with accessibility standards (e.g., WCAG) is ensured through regular testing and audits.

Cross-browser and cross-device compatibility is achieved through responsive design and compatibility testing.

8.3.12. Deployment and Monitoring

For deployment, the application utilizes a mix of cloud platforms and on-premises servers, depending on specific requirements and constraints. The deployment strategy for the first production release (version 1.6.0) includes:

Backend services are deployed on Render, providing scalable and reliable hosting for the server-side components.

The database is hosted on an m0 Atlas cluster, ensuring high availability and data integrity.

Frontend components are deployed on Netlify, leveraging its efficient hosting infrastructure and continuous deployment capabilities.

While continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines are not currently implemented, they are part of the roadmap for future iterations. The project primarily relies on manual deployment processes for now.

Monitoring tools and alerting systems are in place to track system performance, detect issues, and facilitate proactive maintenance. These tools help ensure the stability and reliability of the deployed system.

8.4. Documentation and Support

Detailed documentation is maintained for various components, including installation guides, API documentation, and user manuals. Technical documentation, such as architecture diagrams and design documents, is kept up-to-date. Support channels (e.g., forums, email, chat) are available for users and stakeholders to report issues or seek assistance. All documentation and release notes can be found in the [Docs directory](#) in the GitHub repository.

9. User manual

9.1. Regular User

Figure 43 User manual home page

After browsing the web application URL on any browser, the user meets the home page as usual. The user will find the air quality forecast on this page as the main component. Also, the weather map, quick links to important sites, the averages of air quality, and the metrological data for the latest 24 hours are included. Additionally, users can like or dislike the forecast that the website provides.

Figure 44 User manual about page

Then the user meets the 'About' page and this page has a complete description of the application and the author. This page includes a contact form and the users can contact the platform using Google sign-in. Also, this page includes the most important part called the User Registration. The user can request an account after clicking the 'Sign up Today' button and filling popping form.

Figure 45 User manual sign up process

The user meets the next component as 'Pages'. Pages include 5 different pages called,

1. Reference
2. Feedback
3. FAQ
4. Privacy Policy
5. Terms and Conditions

The Reference page includes all references related to building this platform and important stages of the development process.

Users need to be authorized by Google before entering the Feedback page. After that authorized users can view feedback that users provided before they user able to submit feedback. It's a very easy step. Just type feedback and send it.

Figure 46 User manual feedback

The FAQ page includes frequently asked questions and these questions might be updated and newly added. Also includes the same thing as the 'Privacy Policy' page and 'Terms and Conditions' page. All of these pages are up to date and users can view the last updated date at the bottom of the page.

Additionally, the user meets a tab with a couple of locations and they are the districts based on how this platform works. The user finds that location on Google Maps directly when clicking the location.

Figure 47 User manual dashboard login

The last option for the regular user is to find the 'Dashboard' page. This page has two options sign in and sign up. If the user has an approved account, the user can log in to the system. If else the user can request an account by clicking the sign-up button and can wait to approve the account system administration.

9.2. Registered User

If the user account is approved, the user gets an email notification with default credentials to authorize the dashboard. After successfully logging in to the system the user becomes the welcome page with a wide range of options. The first option is 'Monitoring'. This option allows the user to monitor the latest air quality data according to the selected districts in Sri Lanka. Also, the users are allowed to visit the last 3 months' data and can filter them by districts.

Timestamp	Location	Received Value
2024-04-24 15:18:01	Hambantota	26.73944640530558
2024-04-24 15:21:01	Matara	24.06121134225801
2024-04-24 15:24:01	Matara	25.307336119530063
2024-04-24 15:27:01	Matara	21.713939724020523

Figure 48 User manual monitor air quality

The next step is users are allowed to monitor meteorological data. This option works the same as the above option (air quality monitoring)

Timestamp	Location	Received Value
2024-04-24 15:24:02	Park	24.741893984661836
2024-04-24 15:27:02	Residential	22.71989079449221
2024-04-24 15:30:02	Residential	29.309271423115458
2024-04-24 15:33:02	Commercial	24.879306774063004

Figure 49 User manual monitor metrological

The next step is the most important in this application and we are allowing the users to make predictions about air quality and meteorological data. After mastering this technique, users can identify air quality and metrological patterns between different factors. Before using this option we are providing a user guide to the users to how to do those predictions.

Guidance to make predictions

- First you need to understand how air quality and metrological data work
- Use [Monitoring](#) or [Metrological Data](#) tabs to learn how data work on selected areas. You can use this feature to get unknown factor values using known factor values. This feature is recommended for experienced analyzers. Start your prediction below!
- Choose what's you need to predict(Air quality factor or Metrological factor)
- Select the factor you need to predict from selection
- Enter the values to all required input fields(you can use any real value(21.234568904))

Figure 50 User manual predicting guide

After that, users can move to the air quality tab or meteorological tab and then make predictions.

Figure 51 User manual predicting

Then users can move to the next stage called 'Statistical Analysis'. In this option, we are allowing users to study the air quality and meteorological data with a statistical phase including calculating the median, mode, mean, and correlations.

Figure 52 User manual statistical analysis

In the next step we are allowing users to monitor the air quality data and the meteorological data by using a various range of graphs. Users can select the factor need to monitor, select the size of data and finally select the type of graph.

Figure 53 User manual load graphs

Finally, registered users are allowed to account settings including the change credentials option and delete account options.

Figure 54 User manual log in to administration

9.3. Administration

We are conducting live session for administration of this application after releasing the production to the client. In that session we will explain everything to the administration and we will provide 3 free live sessions to the administration. But for further knowledge we are documenting administration options as follows.

1. Forecast management

Forecast management has options to create new forecast, edit current forecast, save or discard draft, change visibility, delete and preview before publishing.

2. User Management

In the user management administration allows to view users list, delete users or accept users' requests, communicate with other admins and request to the new administration through the HR department.

3. Blogs Management

Administration can create, view, edit and delete blogs. These blogs are supports to html and markdown language formats. (Hints are included)

4. Feedback management

The administration can delete unwanted feedback. This is causing an ethical confusion. But on the platform's side, malicious feedback can mud on the organization's name. For this case, I thought the most important thing is organization and my first duty is to keep the organization stand.

5. Comments Management

But in this case is more difficult to make a single decision for me. The reason is preventing someone's idea or comment is an unethical step. So I stopped developing options to handle comments and marked them as under development. As a developer, I can build those options after getting stakeholders' and lawyers' permission in writing.

6. FAQ Management

FAQ management works same as the Blog management and this option includes creating new FAQs, loading the current list, and updating FAQs.

7. System Settings and User Settings

Under this phase, the administration can create or update the user policy and user terms. The most important thing is that once created the policy or terms, it cannot be undone. After creating the policy or terms administration only allows to update them. In addition, the administration has settings for their account for changing credentials and deleting accounts.

10.SLA (Service Level Agreement)

10.1. Availability

10.1.1. Uptime

Urban Air Quality Platform strives to maintain a high level of availability for the Platform. We guarantee an uptime of 99.9% over a rolling 12-month period, excluding scheduled maintenance.

10.1.2. Scheduled Maintenance

Scheduled maintenance may occasionally be required to ensure the continued performance and security of the Platform. Urban Air Quality Platform will provide advance notice of scheduled maintenance whenever possible, and such maintenance will not be counted against the uptime guarantee.

10.2. Performance

10.2.1. Response Time

Urban Air Quality Platform aims to provide a responsive user experience on the Platform. We commit to maintaining an average response time of under 500 milliseconds for all user requests.

10.2.2. Error Rate

Urban Air Quality Platform monitors the error rate of the Platform to ensure reliability. We guarantee an error rate of less than 0.1% for all user interactions.

10.3. Support

10.3.1. Customer Support

Urban Air Quality Platform provides customer support services to address any issues or concerns users may encounter while using the Platform. Our support team is available during standard business hours to assist users with technical or operational inquiries.

10.3.2. Response Time for Support Requests

We commit to responding to user support requests within 24 hours of receipt during standard business hours. Urgent or critical issues will be addressed with the highest priority.

10.4. Data Security and Privacy

10.4.1. Data Encryption

Urban Air Quality Platform employs industry-standard encryption protocols to protect user data transmitted over the Platform. All data stored on our servers is encrypted to ensure confidentiality and integrity.

10.4.2. Compliance with Privacy Regulations

We comply with all applicable privacy regulations and laws governing the collection, storage, and processing of user data. Urban Air Quality Platform is committed to safeguarding the privacy and security of user information.

10.5. Service Credits

In the event of a breach of the uptime guarantee specified in Section 1.1, Urban Air Quality Platform may, at its discretion, issue service credits to affected users. Service credits will be calculated based on the duration and severity of the outage.

10.6. Termination

This SLA is effective upon the commencement of service and remains in effect until terminated by either party. Either party may terminate this agreement with 30 days' written notice.

11.Privacy Policy

1. Introduction

Welcome to our Air Quality Monitoring and Prediction Platform. This Privacy Policy outlines how we collect, use, disclose, and manage your personal information when you use our platform. By accessing or using our platform, you agree to the terms outlined in this Privacy Policy.

2. Information We Collect

We may collect personal information that you provide to us voluntarily when you use our platform. This information may include:

- Name
- Email Address
- Location Data
- Usage Data
- Any other information you provide voluntarily

3. How We Use Your Information

We use the information collected for the following purposes:

- To provide and maintain our platform
- To personalize your experience
- To improve our platform and services
- To communicate with you
- To comply with legal obligations

4. How We Share Your Information

We may share your personal information with third parties for the following purposes:

Service Providers: We may share your information with third-party service providers who assist us in operating our platform.

Legal Compliance: We may disclose your information in response to legal requests or to comply with applicable laws and regulations.

5. Data Security

We implement security measures to protect your personal information from unauthorized access, alteration, disclosure, or destruction. However, no method of transmission over the internet or electronic storage is 100% secure.

6. Your Rights

You have the right to access, update, or delete your personal information. If you wish to exercise these rights or have any questions about our Privacy Policy, please contact us at kavindu.kokila.info@gmail.com.

7. Changes to this Privacy Policy

We may update our Privacy Policy from time to time. We will notify you of any changes by posting the new Privacy Policy on this page. You are advised to review this Privacy Policy periodically for any changes.

12. Terms and Conditions

1. Acceptance of Terms

By accessing or using our platform, you agree to be bound by these Terms and Conditions. If you do not agree to these terms, you may not use our platform.

2. Use of Platform

You may use our platform for lawful purposes only. You are responsible for ensuring that your use of the platform complies with all applicable laws and regulations.

3. Intellectual Property

All content and materials available on our platform, including but not limited to text, graphics, logos, images, and software, are the property of Urban Air Quality Platform and are protected by intellectual property laws.

4. Disclaimer of Warranties

Our platform is provided on an "as is" and "as available" basis, without any warranties of any kind, express or implied. We do not warrant that our platform will be error-free or uninterrupted, or that any defects will be corrected.

5. Limitation of Liability

In no event shall Urban Air Quality Platform be liable for any indirect, incidental, special, or consequential damages arising out of or in any way connected with your use of our platform.

6. Governing Law

These Terms and Conditions shall be governed by and construed in accordance with the laws of Sri Lanka, without regard to its conflict of law provisions.

7. Contact Us

If you have any questions about these Terms and Conditions, please contact us at kavindu.kokila.info@gmail.com.

Chapter 09

13. Lessons Learned

1. Importance of Clear Requirements

Lesson: Clear and well-defined requirements are essential for the success of a project. Ambiguities or misunderstandings in requirements can lead to delays, scope creep, and ultimately, project failure.

Action Taken: Conduct thorough requirement-gathering conversations with the supervisor to ensure alignment and understanding of project objectives and deliverables.

2. Effective Communication

Lesson: Effective communication is crucial for project success. Regular communication among team members and the supervisor helps to identify issues early, resolve conflicts, and ensure everyone is aligned with project goals.

Action Taken: Implemented regular status discussions, progress reports, and communication channels to keep the supervisor informed and address any concerns promptly.

3. Importance of Testing

Lesson: Testing is a critical aspect of software development. Comprehensive testing helps to identify bugs, errors, and usability issues before deployment, leading to a more reliable and stable product.

Action Taken: Implemented a rigorous testing process, including unit tests, integration tests, and user acceptance testing, to ensure the quality and reliability of the software.

4. Flexibility and Adaptability

Lesson: Projects often encounter unforeseen challenges and changes. Flexibility and adaptability are key to successfully navigating these challenges and adjusting the course as needed.

Action Taken: Embraced an agile development approach, allowing for iterative development, frequent feedback, and adaptation to changing requirements and priorities.

14.Future Recommendations

1. Continuous Improvement

Recommendation: Emphasize a culture of continuous improvement within the team. Encourage learning from past experiences, adopting new technologies and best practices, and striving for excellence in all aspects of project execution.

Actionable Steps: Implement regular retrospectives to review project performance, identify areas for improvement, and implement action plans for addressing issues and optimizing processes.

2. Enhanced Documentation

Recommendation: Improve documentation practices to ensure clarity, completeness, and accessibility of project documentation. Well-documented code, design documents, user manuals, and other artifacts facilitate knowledge transfer, collaboration, and future maintenance.

Actionable Steps: Develop standardized templates and guidelines for documentation, assign responsibility for document creation and maintenance, and conduct regular reviews to ensure accuracy and relevance.

3. Invest in Training and Development

Recommendation: Invest in training and development opportunities for team members to enhance their skills, knowledge, and expertise. Continuous learning and professional development contribute to individual growth and the overall success of the project.

Actionable Steps: Provide access to training programs, workshops, conferences, and certifications relevant to the project and team members' roles. Encourage a culture of learning and knowledge sharing within the team.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I would mention again air pollution is a big trouble increasing day by day. The main cause is this problem is the ignorance of the people about air quality. Also, people think maintaining clean air is a government or organization's responsibility only. But every living being has a part of a contribution to maintaining clean air.

In my Proposal, I'm focusing on giving knowledge to people on how valuable is quality air and what are the factors and qualities of their living area. Also, I'm gonna give a learning platform for people to analyze, calculate, and predict air quality factors around them. This is the main conclusion of my project proposal I believe knowledge is power and if we use knowledge for doing good, we can make the world a better place.

The goal of this project is to address the most concerning environmental issue at this time by providing a robust geographic analysis platform that is easy to use. Consequently, the burgeoning air quality problem worldwide manifests itself in the deterioration of the air and the health and environmental implications. Thus, a growing need for user-friendly instruments to monitor and predict air quality has risen. This project intends to make people aware of the quality of air around their area by giving them tools to assess their air quality which will encourage them to feel empowered to take action and campaign for cleaner air.

An important role of this project is its capability to erase the distance between theory and practice. Making use of data and analytics, individuals can now visualize and interpret air quality information, therefore being able to make suitable decisions preventing them from negative health and well-being effects. Also, the platform's forecasting utilities provide valuable findings to understand the trends in air quality that can allow for preventive measures to address pollution and lessen the effects of pollution on public health and the environment.

What is more, the project is an on-the-spot measure for combating the major problem which is air pollution. By sensitizing, educating, and mobilizing the community we can turn individuals from passive bystanders to engaged and active Guardians of the environment, thus contributing to a cleaner and healthier world.

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Appendix 1

4/29/24, 2:54 PM TurnitinUK - Originality Report - moodle.docx

TurnitinUK Originality Report

Processed on: 29-Apr-2024 10:02 AM BST
ID: 231266668
Word Count: 18439
Submitted: 1

Similarity Index 6%	Similarity by Source Internet Sources: 5% Publications: 1% Student Papers: 5%
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moodle.docx By KAVINDU KOKILA
GAYASHAN SIRIWARDHANA LIYANAGE

< 1% match (student papers from 05-Oct-2022)
[Submitted to University of Wales Institute, Cardiff on 2022-10-05](#)

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[Submitted to University of Wales Institute, Cardiff on 2023-12-29](#)

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[Submitted to The University of Wales Trinity Saint David on 2024-03-15](#)

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<https://morrisbiasinitiativesllc.com/>

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[Submitted to University of South Australia on 2019-06-19](#)

< 1% match (Internet from 02-Jan-2022)
<http://www.aacegulf.org/wpautoterms/>

< 1% match (Internet from 11-Mar-2024)

Appendix 2

Resources

Source code – [view or clone](#)

Model evaluation and statistical analysis (dataset) - [jupyter](#) (gist)

High quality diagrams and images – [view and download](#) (open drawios on drawio platform to check - [drawio](#))

Performance report - [download](#)

Release notes and docs - [view](#)

Configuration guide - [view](#)

Test documentation for python - [view](#)

API documentation - [view](#)

Production - [run](#) (Gets up to 3munites to start server in very first attempt)

Development stats

2024-01-19

Latest (2024-04-45)

CI/CD workflow stats (Passed)

Complete project stats

kavicastelo / Ethical-AI-driven-Geographic-Analytics-Platform
159 MB

👁️ 1
★ 1
👤 2

ai angular java mongodb py4j python spring-boot

This is a web-based Air Quality Monitoring and AI prectioning platform. I used Angular and Spring-Boot tech stack to build the project. Also used Python as a supportive language too.

urban-air-quality-monitor.netlify.app

Repo health (100%)

- ✔️ Readme
- ✔️ GNU General Public License v3.0
- ✔️ Code of conduct (Contributor Covenant)
- ✔️ Contribution guidelines
- ❌ No issue template
- ✔️ Pull request template

Package

No npm package detected in the project root.

Commits (583 last year)

Ethical-AI-driven-Geographic-Analytics-Platform Sort by Type Filter

Files

📁 .idea	305 (0.5%)
📁 .mavn	3 (0.0%)
📁 AI_Models	12 (0.0%)
📁 Docs	2,515 (3.8%)
📁 client	56,157 (85.9%)
📁 src	4,679 (7.2%)
📄 .env	9 (0.0%)
📄 .gitignore	31 (0.0%)
📄 Dockerfile	38 (0.1%)
📄 README.md	253 (0.4%)
📄 improved_air_quality_data.csv	389 (0.6%)
📄 improved_meteorological_da...	389 (0.6%)
📄 land_use_data.csv	5 (0.0%)
📄 mvnw	278 (0.4%)
📄 mvnw.cmd	169 (0.3%)
📄 pom.xml	109 (0.2%)
📄 requirements.txt	8 (0.0%)

Lines of code (65,349)

.json	39,770 (60.9%)
.ts	7,657 (11.7%)
.java	4,223 (6.5%)
.html	3,383 (5.2%)
.md	3,142 (4.8%)
.css	2,934 (4.5%)
.scss	1,583 (2.4%)
.csv	783 (1.2%)
.py	437 (0.7%)
.txt	340 (0.5%)
mvnw	278 (0.4%)
.xml	274 (0.4%)
.cmd	169 (0.3%)
.iml	140 (0.2%)
.gitignore	66 (0.1%)
Dockerfile	38 (0.1%)
.png	36 (0.1%)
.jpg	28 (0.0%)
.properties	21 (0.0%)
.editorconfig	13 (0.0%)
.pkl	12 (0.0%)
.env	9 (0.0%)
.gif	6 (0.0%)
.js	3 (0.0%)
.ico	2 (0.0%)
.fig	1 (0.0%)
.jar	1 (0.0%)
.gitkeep	0 (0.0%)

Deployment stats

Database

Backend

Frontend

Appendix 3

Operation alignment of the study

Variable	Question	Indicator	Source
Public awareness on urban air quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How well do you understand the concept of urban air quality and its impact on public health? 	1. Five point Likert scale	(Heffernan, O. M., & Páez, A., 2018)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How aware are you of the various sources of air pollution in urban areas (e.g., vehicles, industrial emissions, construction)? 	2. Five point Likert scale	(Semenza, J. C., & Wilson, D. J., 2008)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent are you concerned about the health effects of poor urban air quality (e.g., respiratory problems, cardiovascular diseases)? 	3. Five point Likert scale	(Whitmarsh, L., & O'Neill, S., 2010)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you perceive the efforts made by local authorities to improve urban air quality? 	4. Five point Likert scale	(Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How likely are you to engage in actions to reduce your contribution to urban air pollution (e.g., using public transportation, reducing energy consumption)? 	5. Five point Likert scale	(Steg et al., 2014)
Traditional media campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How frequently have you seen or heard traditional media advertisements (e.g., television commercials, radio announcements, newspaper articles) about urban air quality? 	6. Five point Likert scale	(Zhao, X., & Briones, R. L., 2009)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How effective do you think the traditional media campaign has been in raising awareness about urban air quality issues? 	7. Five point Likert scale	(Van Steenburg, E., & Wagstaff, M. F., 2019)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much new information have you learned about urban air quality as a result of the traditional media campaign? 	8. Five point Likert scale	(Kahlor, L. A., 2010)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent are you motivated to take actions to improve urban air quality based on the information provided by the campaign? 	9. Five point Likert scale	(Maibach et al., 2008)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How satisfied are you with the traditional media campaign's efforts to inform the public about urban air quality? 	10. Five point Likert scale	(Gutteling, J. M., 2013)
Community engagement workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How frequently have you attended community workshops or events focused on urban air quality? 	11. Five point Likert scale	(Ellis et al., 2019)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How relevant do you find the information presented in the 	12. Five point Likert scale	(Nisbet, M. C., & Scheufele, D. A., 2009)

	community workshops to be regarding urban air quality?		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How much new information have you learned about urban air quality as a result of attending community workshops? 	13. Five point Likert scale	(Besley et al., 2018)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent are you motivated to engage in behaviors that contribute to improving urban air quality after participating in community workshops? 	14. Five point Likert scale	(Stern, P. C., 2000)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How satisfied are you with your overall experience attending community workshops on urban air quality? 	15. Five point Likert scale	(Flay et al., 2009)

Collaboration with schools and educational institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How frequently have you participated in educational programs or activities related to urban air quality organized by schools or educational institutions? 	16. Five point Likert scale	(Stevenson et al., 2014)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How effective do you perceive the educational programs conducted by schools or educational institutions to be in raising awareness about urban air quality issues? 	17. Five point Likert scale	(McCrea, R., & Booth, A., 2018)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How much new knowledge have you acquired about urban air quality as a result of collaborating with schools or educational institutions? 	18. Five point Likert scale	(Chen, X., & Zhang, Y., 2019)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent are you motivated to advocate for measures that improve urban air quality after participating in collaborations with schools or educational institutions? 	19. Five point Likert scale	(Schultz, P. W., 2002)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How satisfied are you with the collaborative efforts between your community and schools/educational institutions regarding urban air quality awareness? 	20. Five point Likert scale	(Kaiser et al., 1999)
Online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How aware are you of the existence of the online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality? 	21. Five point Likert scale	(Kruger, J., & Dunning, D., 1999)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How often do you visit or use the online web platform to check urban air quality information? 	22. Five point Likert scale	(Lebo et al., 2013)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How accurate do you perceive the information provided by the online web platform regarding urban air quality? 	23. Five point Likert scale	(Tandoc et al., 2018)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To what extent do you trust the online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality? 	24. Five point Likert scale	(Lee, E., & Shin, S. Y., 2014)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How useful do you find the online web platform in helping you make decisions or take actions regarding urban air quality? 	25. Five point Likert scale	(Venkatesh et al., 2012)
Demographic factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which of the following best describes your age? 	26. Array	(Taylor, 2023)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which of the following genders do you most 	27. Two types	(Taylor, 2023)

	identify with?		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which of the following best describes your employment status? 	28. Six types	(Taylor, 2023)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which of the following best describes your living area? 	29. Five types	Kavindu Kokila

Questioner

I am an undergraduate student of the ICBT. I am currently carrying out a research study on the topic.

"Factors that Effect On Public Awareness On Urban Air Quality".

This is part of the requirements for my graduation and award of a BSc BIS degree by the Cardiff Metropolitan University.

Kindly fill out the questionnaire as honestly and objectively as possible. All information supplied will be treated with utmost confidentiality and used mainly for academic purposes.

Thank you in advance for your co-operation.

Public awareness on urban air quality

How well do you understand the concept of urban air quality and its impact on public health?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How aware are you of the various sources of air pollution in urban areas (e.g., vehicles, industrial emissions, construction)?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

To what extent are you concerned about the health effects of poor urban air quality (e.g., respiratory problems, cardiovascular diseases)?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How do you perceive the efforts made by local authorities to improve urban air quality?				
Ineffective	Somewhat Effective	Moderately Effective	Effective	Very Effective

How likely are you to engage in actions to reduce your contribution to urban air pollution (e.g., using public transportation, reducing energy consumption)?				
Very Unlikely	Unlikely	Neutral	Likely	Very Likely

Traditional media campaigns

How frequently have you seen or heard traditional media advertisements (e.g., television commercials, radio announcements, newspaper articles) about urban air quality?				
Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently

How effective do you think the traditional media campaign has been in raising awareness about urban air quality issues?				
Not Effective at All	Somewhat Ineffective	Neutral	Somewhat Effective	Very Effective

How much new information have you learned about urban air quality as a result of the traditional media campaign?				
None	A Little	Some	A Lot	A Great Deal

To what extent are you motivated to take actions to improve urban air quality based on the information provided by the campaign?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How satisfied are you with the traditional media campaign's efforts to inform the public about urban air quality?				
Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied

Community engagement workshops

How frequently have you attended community workshops or events focused on urban air quality?				
Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently

How relevant do you find the information presented in the community workshops to be regarding urban air quality?				
Not Relevant at All	Somewhat Irrelevant	Neutral	Somewhat Relevant	Very Relevant

How much new information have you learned about urban air quality as a result of attending community workshops?				
None	A Little	Some	A Lot	A Great Deal

To what extent are you motivated to engage in behaviors that contribute to improving urban				
--	--	--	--	--

air quality after participating in community workshops?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How satisfied are you with your overall experience attending community workshops on urban air quality?				
Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied

Collaboration with schools and educational institutions

How frequently have you participated in educational programs or activities related to urban air quality organized by schools or educational institutions?				
Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently

How effective do you perceive the educational programs conducted by schools or educational institutions to be in raising awareness about urban air quality issues?				
Not Effective at All	Somewhat Ineffective	Neutral	Somewhat Effective	Very Effective

How much new knowledge have you acquired about urban air quality as a result of collaborating with schools or educational institutions?				
None	A Little	Some	A Lot	A Great Deal

To what extent are you motivated to advocate for measures that improve urban air quality after participating in collaborations with schools or educational institutions?				
Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely

How satisfied are you with the collaborative efforts between your community and schools/educational institutions regarding urban air quality awareness?				
Very Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neutral	Satisfied	Very Satisfied

Dissatisfied				
--------------	--	--	--	--

Online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality

How aware are you of the existence of the online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality?				
Not at all aware	Slightly aware	Moderately aware	Very aware	Extremely aware

How often do you visit or use the online web platform to check urban air quality information?				
Never	Rarely	Occasionally	Frequently	Very Frequently

How accurate do you perceive the information provided by the online web platform regarding urban air quality?				
Not accurate at all	Slightly accurate	Moderately accurate	Very accurate	Extremely accurate

To what extent do you trust the online web platform for monitoring and predicting urban air quality?				
Do not trust at all	Slightly trust	Moderately trust	Very trust	Completely trust

How useful do you find the online web platform in helping you make decisions or take actions regarding urban air quality?				
Not useful at all	Slightly useful	Moderately useful	Very useful	Extremely useful

Demographic factors

Which of the following best describes your age?				
Under 18	18 to 24	25 to 34	35 to 44	45 and over

Which of the following genders do you most identify with?	
Male	Female

Which of the following best describes your employment status?					
Employed full-time	Employed part-time	Student	Disabled	Retired	Unemployed

Which of the following best describes your living area?				
Community	rural	suburb	suburban	urban